

PRO-CLIMATE

Proactive community adaptation to climate change through social transformation and behavioural change

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D5.2 Multi-Agent Computer Model

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Abbreviations

EC	European Commission
eNGO	Environmental NGO
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
HUMAT	Human-Automated Model
LL	Living Labs
MACM	Multi-Agent Computer Model
MOA	Motivation, Opportunities, Abilities
REA	European Research Executive Agency
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

This document accompanies the implementation of the PRO-CLIMATE multi-agent computer model (MACM), providing an accessible explanation of its structure, logic, and purpose. The strategic objective of PRO-CLIMATE is to support communities to proactively adapt to climate change through social transformation and behavioural change. In this context, the overarching goal of Work Package 5 “Modelling and stress-testing the system” is to develop a generalisable model capable of simulating how community-level behavioural and institutional dynamics influence decisions about land use with environmental implications—specifically, how citizen mobilization and institutional interaction can lead to climate-resilient outcomes. As a second step toward this goal, the present task builds on the outcomes of T5.1 and focuses on creating a model tailored in relation to the Vestland case as this Living Lab (LL) is one out of the six Living Labs to be established within the PRO-CLIMATE project.

Vestland was chosen as the starting point because it was already defined in terms of objectives and identified sources/data availability, while the rest of the cases would have more time to clarify their goal and identify all data sources. Grounding the model in this real-world case ensures that its components are empirically informed and practically relevant. Furthermore, the focus of the Vestland LL on land use changes in the context of tensions between green shift, biodiversity conservation and economic development priorities has relevance across Europe. The next phase of modelling (5.3) will extend the model to the other LLs.

The MACM integrates psychological, social, and institutional components using the HUMAT and MOA frameworks for decision-making. After the MACM is calibrated and validated, additional sensitivity analysis will provide further validation and enable stakeholders to better understand the factors contributing to social tipping points in the Vestland case. While technical in nature, this document is written for a broader audience and aims to describe how these components are operationalized and how they work together to model tipping points in socio-ecological systems.

This model is not definitive. The following WP5 task (T5.3) will work towards the overarching goal of generalisability by evaluating how the insights and processes developed here can be adapted and refined to fit other study cases. This iterative process will involve collaborating closely with stakeholders from these cases to identify common denominators and adapt the model’s components and logic accordingly, ensuring that the final model is robust and not tied to the specifics of the Vestland case alone.

By detailing the agents, their behaviours, and their interactions over time, this report serves as both a conceptual bridge and a practical guide to understanding what the model simulates and why. The PRO-CLIMATE Multi-Agent Computer Model (MACM) implementation is publicly available and can be accessed via the following GitLab repository: <https://gitlab.norceresearch.no/cmss/digital-social-twins/models/pro-climate/-/tree/deliverable-5.2>.

1. Introduction

1.1 Description of WP 5 and the Role of Task 5.2

Work Package 5 (WP5), Modelling and Stress Testing the System, aims to develop a multi-agent computer model (MACM) that captures the dynamics of social-ecological systems (SEs) undergoing climate-related transitions. Drawing on cutting-edge research and empirical input from the PRO-CLIMATE Living Labs, the MACM simulates how various actors—citizens, institutions, media, and NGOs—interact under different environmental and political conditions. The model is designed to identify key social tipping points and leverage actions that could facilitate systemic transformation towards climate resilience across diverse European contexts.

The model serves as the analytical engine for WP5's ultimate goal: a web-based platform for policymakers and stakeholders. This platform will enable in-depth exploration of the model's results, including different scenario testing, allowing users to assess the likely impacts of current and future policy options in their local settings.

Within WP5, Task 5.2 is the central operational task responsible for the construction and implementation of the MACM. It translates the conceptual foundations developed in Task 5.1, including the integration of the HUMAT (Human-Automated Model, see: Jager et al., 2025) and MOA (Motivations, Opportunities, Abilities, see: Maclnnis et al., 1991) behavioural frameworks, into working model code. Task 5.2 is where abstract concepts become concrete mechanisms. This deliverable (D5.2) documents the functioning of the implemented model in accessible terms, describing how agents are designed, how they behave, and how their interactions unfold across time to produce emergent outcomes. By situating the model in one of the living labs (Vestland), Task 5.2 also functions as a first validation of the approach before its generalization to other cases.

1.2 Model Availability

The PRO-CLIMATE Multi-Agent Computer Model (MACM) implementation is publicly available and can be accessed via the following GitLab repository: <https://gitlab.norceresearch.no/cmss/digital-social-twins/models/pro-climate/-/tree/deliverable-5.2>.

2 Case Context: Vestland as a Socio-Ecological System

2.1 Rationale for and Overview of the Vestland case study

'Climate change is admittedly becoming an increasingly important cause of the loss of biodiversity, but land use and land use changes remain the number one cause of such loss.' Norway's Nature Risk Commission Terms of Reference, 2022.

Land use decisions are both critical for adaptation to climate change and can have a major impact on the sustainability of ecosystems and biodiversity (Holland et al., 2019, Auffret & Svenning 2022). WP5 has therefore chosen to focus on modelling how land use decisions are made, beginning with cases from the living lab in Vestland in Norway. The reasons for the latter choice are methodological, logistical and representational. First, methodological - ABMs are typically constructed by working from one case, developing and testing model validity for that case, then adapting or re-calibrating it to fit other cases. This procedure reduces initial complexity, hence facilitating model development, and ensures model relevance to real life cases. We chose to start with Vestland because the living lab was already well-defined in terms of its objectives and data availability, unlike many of the other study cases that were still in the process of clarifying their goals and data sources. Third, care was taken to ensure that the case focused on a topic – the interaction between the green shift, nature conservation and growth priorities - that is significant across Europe (Holland et al., 2019, Auffret & Svenning 2022). Furthermore, we consulted with partners to ensure that in each of the other locations where living labs were planned there were suitable cases to enable comparison and hence the development of the model towards generalisation. In other words, we took care to use a first case that both represented a significant issue across Europe and enabled comparison with other living labs, widening the model's relevance at a European scale.

Partners also decided to model the formation of opposition to land development proposals by environmental activists as part of the social-ecological system. Such opposition may not be significant or present in every scenario – in which case the impact of this element can be set low or to zero within the model. However, contemporary conditions - a combination of increased opposition to Green Shift policies across European (Bocquillon 2024), mounting evidence of anthropogenic climate change and increasing willingness of activists to use more radical protest forms (Jansma et al. 2025) suggests that conflict over land-use decision making is likely to increase over time, with protest by activists forming part of the picture. Giving planners and policy makers a tool to model the formation and impact of such groups is therefore a valuable goal.

Turning to the Vestland LL, PRO-CLIMATE is engaged with stakeholders involved in multiple facets of land-use decision-making across Vestland, a geographically large (330,000 sq. km), mountainous and fjorded western-most county of Norway. It is sparsely populated (20 persons/sq.km) except for the port city of Bergen where almost half of the county's 638,821 population (289,330) live in an area of just 465 sq. km. Vestland's population has grown rapidly in recent decades (up 8.1% between 2011-2021), creating substantial pressures on land for residential, infrastructure and commercial development, especially around Bergen. More rural areas face different challenges, with local politicians and the business community often keen to bring new developments that will create local jobs and keep young people in these areas. The 'green shift' away from Norway's heavily oil-based economy also brings new pressure on land, with facilities for carbon and methane capture built and planned on sites opposed by environmentalists and plans to build onshore windfarms and pylons to carry electricity encountering opposition. Climate modelling predicts that Bergen, already Europe's wettest city, will experience increased precipitation in future years, meaning that the risks associated with depleting natural resources like wetlands (which hold water and mitigate the risks of flooding and landslip) increase, highlighting the need to conserve them and implement other water management strategies.

While PRO-CLIMATE is engaged with government, planners, businesses and environmental NGOs across Vestland and developing a living lab process involving stakeholders with diverse perspectives

on several planning controversies across the region, the pilot model has been developed around the case of the Kildn proposal to build a new dock for cruise ships and an electric boat transport hub in the Eidsvika area of Askøy island, just west of Bergen, with fieldwork and interview data collected by researchers from PRO-CLIMATE's sister project Pro-Coast combined with data gathered by the Pro-Climate team. It draws on data gathered by mixed methods, including fieldwork observations, stakeholder interviews, document analysis (of political platforms, area plans and planning policy) literature review and a synthetic population composed from representative surveys from the Norwegian Citizen Panel. More than 20 interviews with key stakeholders, including local politicians (who play a key role in land use decision-making), the island's mayor, the business consortium proposing the development, environmental activists, regional planners, state representatives and consultation with scientific experts (thus corresponding to the four constituencies of the Quadruple Helix Model (QHM, Galvao et al., 2019).

The Kildn proposal was proposed to Askøy council by Tertnes holdings, a local business consortium, and is unusual for a major infrastructure proposal not to emerge from regional and national planning processes. However, the case is typical not just for Norway but of many European contexts where a desire to attract investment to boost the local economy stands in tension with concerns about the implications of development for ecosystem sustainability and biodiversity. The case also features strong connections between local businesses and politicians whose objectives are sometimes in tension with regional and national authorities, quite similar to tensions experienced European planning systems. Despite receiving advice to reject the proposal from regional authorities' state and regional authorities (Statsforvalteren, Fylke), local politicians have repeatedly put the Kildn proposal back into the local plan. The proposal is also opposed by the group Eidsvikas Venner (Eidsvika's Friends), an offshoot of the local Naturverdforbundet (Friends of the Earth) chapter. Such dynamics making the case a rich microcosm to investigate the dynamics of local land-use decision making in a European democracy critical to proactive climate change adaptation.

2.2 Relevance for modelling proactive adaptation and land use decisions

While Norway's land use decision making is specific, it features many similar structures and pressures found across Europe. Local councils have considerable autonomy in land-use decision making, and although the national state's representative (Statsforvalteren) can over-rule under certain circumstances, they are reluctant to exercise these powers, meaning that local decisions can sometimes be at variance with national policy goals. This reluctance springs from a desire to respect local democracy, from a perceived lack of legitimacy of regional political structures in Norway, and from political differences between rural Western councils, including Askøy, and the Oslo-based national government with its seat in Eastern Norway, which the Statsforvalteren represents. Scepticism about the legitimacy of regional government also impacts on elected Fylke (Vestland regional authority).

Green policies are also threatened in Bergen, with the municipality's climate department halved and downgraded after elections in 2024, and planners informed that the previous administration's commitment to 'area neutrality' (not building on new areas or balancing new developments with restoration work) will not be followed. Similar pressures face policy makers across Europe, with a widespread backlash against the European Green Deal (Bocquillon, 2024). By representing as realistically as possible the dynamics between planners, politicians, business NGOs, media and local citizens within the local arena, and the impacts of regional and national advisory bodies, the case provides a working model of a local land use decision-making system in a European democracy, providing a template that can be adapted and recalibrated to a variety of European conditions in the next phases of modelling. To adapt the model to new case studies we will update the synthetic population profiles, adjust media parameters, and use the mapping of stakeholders already undertaken by WP2, 3 and 4 supplemented by additional expert and stakeholder interviews as required.

3 Agent-Based Modelling in PRO-CLIMATE

3.1 Agent-Based Modelling

Agent-Based Modelling (ABM) offers a powerful approach for exploring how individual behaviours, institutional dynamics, and environmental feedbacks interact within complex systems (Balbi & Giupponi, 2010; Beckage et al., 2018; Le et al., 2012; Liu et al., 2020). In the context of climate adaptation, ABMs allow researchers to simulate how diverse actors—such as citizens, policymakers, and NGOs—respond to policy interventions, external shocks, and each other. These simulations reveal how local behaviours can scale into systemic patterns, including tipping points, resistance to change, and emergent coordination.

Compared to traditional top-down models, ABMs excel at representing heterogeneity in values, beliefs, resources, and decision-making strategies (Gilbert et al., 2018; Jager & Edmonds, 2015; Schlüter et al., 2017). This granularity makes them especially well-suited to study behavioural change and governance in socio-ecological systems. As such, ABM has been used to study climate mitigation, energy transitions, land-use conflicts, and adaptation behaviours, but many models lack integration of real-world institutions or psychological realism (Moallemi & Malekpour, 2018; Shults et al., 2025; Tolk et al., 2023).

The PRO-CLIMATE project addresses these gaps by grounding its models in empirical data, institutional structures, and social-behavioural theory. Empirical data such as that from the Norwegian Citizen Survey and the Norwegian Citizen Panel provide a realistic foundation for initializing the synthetic population and calibrating the individuals motivations and abilities influencing behavioral decisions. Institutional structures, including the roles of planners, NGOs, media, and politicians, are explicitly represented in the simulation processes and feedback loops. Social-behavioural theory, captured through frameworks like HUMAT and MOA, ensures that decision-making in the model reflects the cognitive, motivational, opportunity and ability factors that shape real-world adaptation behaviors. This integrated approach enables a richer, more policy-relevant simulation of adaptation pathways (Antosz et al., 2019).

To structure the social complexity of climate-relevant decision-making, the model draws on an Agent/Group/Role (AGR) framework (Ferber et al., 2004). In this structure: (a) agents represent autonomous entities such as individuals, politicians, or organizations; (b) groups define the context within which agents interact, such as municipal government, civil society, or activist environments; (c) roles specify the behaviors and responsibilities agents enact within each group (e.g., citizen as protester, planner as assessor).

This modular approach allows agents to move across contexts, adopt multiple roles, and interact with other agents and artifacts (e.g., proposals, media content). It supports flexible representation of formal governance processes, informal mobilization, and network-driven dynamics.

3.2 Overview of the PRO-CLIMATE MACM

The current PRO-CLIMATE MACM simulates climate-relevant land-use decision processes in the Vestland county. The model includes multiple actor types—citizens, environmental NGOs, media agents, urban planners, and politicians—each embedded in specific environments and roles. These were the key actors identified as the main stakeholders and decision-makers in the Norwegian LL. These agents interact through structured processes that reflect realistic planning and consultation procedures.

At the core of the simulation is a development proposal lifecycle, where land development projects are introduced, assessed, revised, and ultimately approved or rejected. This process is shaped by multiple forms of influence:

- Citizens make decisions about joining activist groups and participating in actions (e.g., protests) based on values, experiences, social networks, and media exposure.
- NGOs employ different actions (e.g., lobbying, awareness campaigns, actions) depending on their resources, experience, and strategic orientation.

- Politicians weigh multiple signals—technical assessments, public opinion, party stance, and NGO pressure—before voting.
- Media agents shape the public discourse through news coverage that influences both public and political attitudes.

This integrated system allows us to explore how climate-resilient decisions can (or fail to) emerge from decentralized, interacting actors with bounded rationality and competing priorities. The following sections describe how the model's core components were operationalized in detail.

4 Population and Agent Initialization

To represent the social landscape of Vestland, the model begins by generating a synthetic population of individual citizen agents. This population is designed to reflect the demographic, motivational, and behavioural diversity observed in empirical survey data from the Norwegian Citizen Panel (NCP) and the Norwegian Citizen Survey (Innbyggerundersøkelsen), using responses from wave 28 and 29 in 2023-2024 for the NCP (Ivarsflaten et al., 2024, 2024) and wave 2024 for the Norwegian Citizen Survey (Direktoratet for forvaltning og økonomistyring & Nese, 2024). Although these source datasets contain personal information, the synthetic population itself is created using machine learning methods that ensure every profile is statistically representative but cannot be traced back to any real individual (Falck, 2025). This approach preserves privacy and aligns with GDPR requirements.

4.1 Synthetic Population Construction

The generation of the synthetic population follows the methodology outlined in Falck (2025). Agents are sampled to mirror Vestland's actual demographic structure, including distributions of age, gender, education, employment status, etc. Beyond demographics, each agent is assigned motivational attributes—including climate concern, nature preservation values, views on economic growth, political trust, and civic engagement (see section 5).

Where appropriate, categorical survey responses are mapped to distributions of motive importance values (ranging from 0 to 1), allowing for nuanced variation in agents' decision profiles. This includes value motives (e.g., environmental concern), experiential motives (e.g., economic security), and social motives (e.g., conformity), each operationalized according to question codes from the NCP and the National Citizen Survey (see section 5).

Agents are also assigned social network ties probabilistically, capturing patterns of age, gender, education and political views homophily. These ego-networks play a key role in social influence processes later in the simulation. Specifically, within HUMAT, an agent's social motive satisfactions dynamically adjust according to the percentage of network members making the same choice, thereby reflecting how peers shape an individual's decisions and social conformity pressures

4.2 Initialization of Behavioral Parameters

Each citizen is embedded with a set of decision-relevant attributes, informed by their synthetic profile. These include:

- Motives' importances weights for the HUMAT model.
- Opportunities and abilities as defined by the MOA framework (e.g., political self-efficacy, system responsiveness, prior civic engagement).
- Media exposure profiles, determining the likelihood of receiving and reacting to different types of news, based on reported sources of political information (e.g., TV, newspapers, social media).

Together, these parameters determine how agents evaluate decisions such as joining an activist group, participating in an action, or supporting a disruptive action. Satisfaction values for each option are drawn from normal distributions, informed by empirical data and tailored to each motive's importance level.

This initialization process ensures that while the agents are simulated, their motivations and constraints reflect empirically grounded diversity—allowing for meaningful heterogeneity in collective dynamics and responsiveness to external stimuli such as media messages or NGO campaigns.

5. Model Integration and Simulation Architecture

5.1 Overview of Simulation Logic

The Multi-Agent Computer Model (MACM) simulates how individual and institutional actors interact over time to shape decisions about land-use proposals that have environmental implications. The model centres around the lifecycle of development proposals, which are introduced into a simulated municipality (e.g., Askøy), evaluated by a network of agents, and either accepted, revised, or rejected based on a complex interplay of behavioural, political, and institutional dynamics.

At its core, the simulation integrates four major agent classes—citizens, environmental NGOs (eNGOs), media, and politicians—alongside key institutional artifacts like land-use proposals, technical assessments, and news items. These agents interact according to behavioural decision models (HUMAT-MOA for citizens, strategic decision rules for institutions) and influence each other through feedback loops and environmental signals.

Each simulation run proceeds in discrete time steps, representing one month. We default to a monthly time-step because it keeps the computational load manageable, but the model can be switched to weekly intervals if greater temporal detail is required. At each time step, agents observe the current state of the system, evaluate their environment, and make decisions accordingly. A full simulation may span 12 or more-time steps and finish when political decision-making processes surrounding a given proposal are completed.

The flow of logic is captured in Figure 1 which shows the sequencing of agent behaviours, their conditions for action, feedback mechanisms, and decision nodes. The rest of this section walks through each stage of the simulation in the order it unfolds.

Figure 1. Model Flow Diagram

5.2 Model Initialization (t = 0)

Before time steps begin, the simulation enters an initialization phase that sets up the agents, institutions, and artifacts that will drive the model.

5.2.1 Population and Context Setup

A synthetic population of citizen agents is generated to reflect the demographic and motivational diversity of the municipality. This population is constructed using data from the Norwegian Citizen Panel (NCP) and the Norwegian Citizen Survey (Innbyggerundersøkelsen) and serves as the foundation for simulating realistic individual behavior and social influence processes (Fig 2). We plan to simulate the entire adult population of Askøy (n~23,000), but when not possible due to computational power limitations, we will create a sample large enough to remain representative of the population.

Figure 2. Structure of Citizen Agent Initialization

Each agent is assigned a set of demographic attributes, including age, gender, education level, and political orientation. These variables inform the construction of social networks. Specifically, networks are formed using demographic homophily principles, where agents are more likely to establish connections with others who share similar characteristics.

In addition to demographic attributes, agents are also initialized with motivational and ability-related attributes. These are mapped from responses to questions about climate concern, economic priorities, and other values or beliefs relevant to climate and economic related decisions, collected in the NCP and the Norwegian Citizen Survey. These responses are used to inform the HUMAT and MOA framework. The HUMAT framework uses them to assign motive importance weights—indicating how much each agent cares about different goals (e.g., environmental protection, economic security, social conformity). Second, the MOA framework translates them into perceived opportunities and abilities. For example, responses about civic engagement or political self-efficacy determine whether an agent feels capable of acting, while employment status reflects time availability (For details about how these responses are converted into values within the HUMAT and MOA frameworks, see section 6).

While demographic variables are not directly used as inputs in all decision rules, they are structurally embedded in the model in two important ways. First, social networks are generated using homophily based on age, gender, education, and political orientation, ensuring realistic patterns of interpersonal connections. Second, the behavioural attributes of agents—such as motive importance values, opportunity and ability constraints (OA variables), and media exposure—are initialized from individual-level responses in nationally representative surveys (the Norwegian Citizen Panel and the Norwegian Citizen Survey).

These responses are not conditioned on demographic variables in the model logic itself, but they are shaped by them in the real world. In other words, while agents in the model do not make decisions because they are young, elderly, male, or female, the way they respond to survey items is likely influenced by such demographic characteristics. By using empirical survey data to generate the synthetic population, the model captures this diversity implicitly, meaning that structural and behavioural variation across demographic lines is preserved in aggregate through response patterns. This allows the model to reflect population-level heterogeneity without requiring demographic categories to be explicitly coded into the decision algorithms.

5.2.2 Institutional Agent Initialization

In addition to the citizen population, the simulation initializes several institutional agents, each with attributes calibrated to the Vestland case study (Fig 3).

Figure 3. Institutional Agents and Their Core Attributes

eNGOs are assigned values for their internal variables: resources (scaled from 0, no resources, to 1, maximum resources), organizational experience (in years), strategic orientation (ranging from 0, fully collaborative, to 1, fully confrontational), and cultural trust (0, no trust, to 1, full trust). In the Vestland case, an eNGO group is already present and therefore initialized at this stage with predefined attributes. However, when upscaling to other cases or exploring alternative scenarios, the simulation may begin without any existing eNGO. In such cases, eNGOs can emerge dynamically during the simulation, and their attributes will be assigned at the time of formation.

Politicians are initialized with their personal stance on development versus sustainability (from -1, fully supporting development, to 1, fully supporting sustainability), party affiliation with corresponding party stance, and a strategic orientation that categorizes them as vote-seeking, policy-seeking, or office-seeking.

Finally, the media agent is initialized with parameters governing its behavior: the frequency of news generation, the likelihood that coverage adopts a pro-environmental or pro-economic tone, and the probability that news is shared across both institutional and social media channels.

5.2.3 Structural Environment Setup

Finally, the simulation initializes the contextual parameters and introduces the development proposal that will structure agent interactions throughout the model.

The political system is set to open by default, following the assumptions of the Vestland case. The proposal artifact—representing a climate-relevant land use development—is then introduced. In the Vestland case implementation, this proposal is predefined and comes with pre-existing evaluations from urban planners and other institutional actors (e.g., environmental NGOs and public consultation bodies). Accordingly, this information is loaded directly at initialization.

In contrast, when the model is upscaled to other cases or used for scenario testing, this stage can include the procedural generation of new proposals and their institutional assessment using the nADICO framework.

With all agents and structures in place, the simulation proceeds to the first-time step ($t = 1$), where behaviors unfold according to the interaction logic described in the next section.

5.3 Simulation Flow per Time Step

After the initialization phase, the simulation proceeds in monthly time steps. At each step, agents interact with the system based on their roles and the current context. The behavior of the simulation varies depending on whether an eNGO is present. If no eNGO exists at the start of the simulation or has yet to form, a simplified loop is followed. If an eNGO is already present or is formed during the simulation, a more complex series of processes unfolds involving eNGO strategies and their influence on citizens and institutions.

The typical simulation runs for 12 time steps, representing one year, after which politicians evaluate the proposal. The full logic is summarized below and shown in Fig 1.

5.3.1 No eNGO Present

If there is no existing eNGO at the beginning of a time step, the simulation first checks whether a group can be formed. Citizens are asked if they want to form an NGO using the HUMAT framework (see Section 5.4). If a sufficient number of citizens are willing to participate, an eNGO is formed. At this point, its internal variables—resources, experience, strategy, and cultural trust—are initialized and citizen members are assigned to a social network. If no eNGO is formed, the simulation proceeds directly to the media process.

5.3.2 Media Process

Each time step includes a media phase. The media agent may generate news items (see Section 6.1). News is always broadcast via conventional media, and with a certain probability, also disseminated through social media.

News items are then delivered to citizens, based on their personal media exposure profiles derived from survey data (Section 6.1.3). If a citizen receives the news, it may update the importance of one or more motives—such as increasing concern for nature or economic growth—depending on the content of the news (Section 6.1.2).

At this point, if the maximum number of time steps has not been reached, a new month begins. If the time limit has been reached, the simulation transitions to the politician decision process (see Section 7.3.8).

5.3.3 eNGO Present: Strategic Action Processes

If an eNGO is already present (either from initialization or formed during the simulation), a series of additional processes occur before the media phase.

Joining the eNGO

If there is an eNGO, citizens decide if they want to join it using the HUMAT framework (see Section 5.4). Citizens joining the eNGO become members and are added to the eNGO social network.

Direct Action Evaluation

The eNGO decides whether it will undertake a direct action (e.g., lobbying, legal challenge). If the action occurs, its intensity is calculated (see Section 7.2.4) and stored. This value later becomes one of the inputs to the political decision algorithm (Section 7.3).

Indirect Actions (news dissemination)

If the eNGO chooses to take an indirect action, it produces and broadcasts a news item. In this case, the eNGO plays the broadcaster role, delivering content through conventional and/or social media (see Section 7.2.5). As with media-generated news, citizen exposure depends on individual media habits, in this case, however, all eNGO members receive the news. Receiving the news may cause adjustments in motive importance (Section 6.1.2).

Protest Action

If the eNGO chooses a protest action, all eNGO members and selected citizens (those linked to eNGO members via the social network) are given the opportunity to participate. Each makes a decision using HUMAT-MOA logic (Section 5.5). Based on who joins, the protest size is calculated, and an intensity value is assigned (Section 7.2.6), which may influence both public perception and future decisions.

Disruptive Protest Action

If a disruptive protest is chosen, a similar process occurs. eNGO members and selected citizens are invited to join and this decision is based via HUMAT (see section 6.6). Protest size and intensity are calculated as before (see section 7.2.7).

5.3.4 Media Process (Revisited)

After all eNGO actions are complete, the simulation proceeds to the media process, identical to that described in Section 7.3.2.

5.3.5 Time Step Conclusion

At the end of the time step, if the predefined number of steps (usually 12) has not been reached, the model advances to the next month. If 12 steps are completed, the simulation enters the final political decision phase.

5.3.6 Final Decision by Politicians

In the final month, politicians make their decisions regarding the proposal using a two-stage algorithm (Section 7.3.1–7.3.3). First, they aggregate inputs from citizens, media, planners, and NGOs to calculate utilities for accepting or rejecting the proposal (Section 7.3.3). Then, they adjust their decisions based on peer alignment and party cohesion.

Once all votes are cast, the proposal is either approved, rejected, or sent for revision. The simulation then ends.

6 Individual Decision-Making: The HUMAT-MOA Framework

Citizen behaviour in the model is driven by the integrated HUMAT-MOA framework, which allows agents to make psychologically realistic decisions while accounting for structural constraints and social influences. This framework was introduced and detailed in Deliverable D5.1; here we provide a brief overview and explain how it has been operationalized for specific decisions in the simulation.

6.1 HUMAT: Motive-Based Choice

The HUMAT model simulates human decision-making by assuming that each agent acts to maximize their total satisfaction across three types of motives:

- Value motives (e.g., concern for nature or climate),
- Experiential motives (e.g., personal convenience, financial security),
- Social motives (e.g., desire to conform to peer behaviours).

Each motive is assigned an importance weight (from 0 to 1) and is associated with a satisfaction score for each behavioural option. These satisfaction values can be static (e.g., derived from empirical means) or dynamic (e.g., updated based on social feedback or media exposure).

An agent evaluates all available options (e.g., join an activist group, protest, remain inactive) by calculating the total satisfaction for each option. If two or more options are close in score, the agent assesses internal dissonance—a measure of conflict between motives—and may adjust their decision using heuristics such as signalling or inquiring within their social network.

6.2 MOA: Motivation, Opportunity, Ability

To better represent behavioral constraints, HUMAT is extended with the MOA framework. Each decision is evaluated not only in terms of motivation, but also:

- Opportunities: external enablers, such as awareness of a protest or presence of a local eNGO group.
- Abilities: internal or social capabilities, such as time availability, civic experience, or perceived political efficacy.

In our model, MOA parameters modulate the satisfaction levels associated with a given behavior. For instance, if an agent is highly concerned about climate change (strong motivation), but is working full-time (low opportunity) and doubts their political impact (low ability), their total satisfaction for joining a protest may be lowered accordingly—even if their values suggest alignment.

6.3 Decision Modules: Behavioral Choices in Context

The following subsections detail how the HUMAT-MOA framework is applied to three key decisions in the simulation:

- Joining an environmental NGO (6.4)
- Participating in a protest (6.5)
- Engaging in a disruptive protest (6.6)

Each module is informed by survey data from the Norwegian Citizen Panel (the verbatim wording of all questions used is listed in Appendix 1). The modules specify the relevant motives and opportunity/ability constraints. These decisions are dynamically shaped by social networks and media exposure, allowing agents to adapt over time (Fig. 4).

Figure 4. Mapping of NCP data to HUMAT-MOA decision making

6.4 Forming/joining an Environmental NGO

The first behavioral decision modeled is whether citizens want to create an eNGO, if none exists. If one exists they decide on joining an environmental NGO. The decisions are made using the HUMAT-MOA framework and is empirically grounded in data from the Norwegian Citizen Panel (NCP), particularly the 2023–2024 waves.

Each citizen agent weighs satisfaction associated with joining or not joining, based on the importance of different motives. These motives are derived from NCP questions and are categorized as value, experiential, or social. The model then adjusts satisfaction using opportunity and ability variables (from the MOA framework), depending on the agent’s circumstances.

6.4.1 Motives and Their Empirical Mapping

Each motive is tied to one or more NCP questions (Table 1). Responses are mapped according to the selected reply, with values ranging from 0 (lowest importance) to 1 (highest importance). For example, a response of “Not at all worried” is assigned a low importance value (e.g., around 0.0), while “Very worried” is assigned a high importance value (e.g., close to 1.0).

The importance of the conformity motive is not based on survey data but is set according to cultural assumptions. It reflects how much agents care about aligning with peers and can vary by scenario. This is informed by Gelfand et al. (2011), who show that tighter cultures place greater emphasis on norm adherence than looser ones. Although the study covers 33 countries worldwide, it includes a number of European cases (e.g., Norway, Germany, Spain, Greece, UK, Poland), and the published tightness–looseness scores provide an empirical starting point for setting the parameter. The importance of this motive is thus defined as a scenario parameter, allowing the model to explore variation in norm sensitivity across different cultural settings; the value can be adjusted during calibration if evidence suggests a different level of cultural tightness.

Motive Type	NCP Question
Climate Concern	“How worried are you about climate change?”
Nature Concern	“How worried are you about the degradation of nature?”
Economic Security	“How would you assess your own financial situation?”
Growth-First Belief	“Economic growth should be safeguarded even if it conflicts...”

Table 1. Mapping of Motivational Factors for eNGO Membership Decision. Each motive is linked to a question in the Norwegian Citizen Panel (NCP). Responses are translated into an importance value on a scale from 0 (not important) to 1 (very important).

6.4.2 Satisfaction Values for Joining and Not Joining an eNGO

Once motive importances are set, the model calculates the satisfaction each agent would experience from either joining or not joining an eNGO. Satisfaction values are derived from rationales grounded in theory. For instance, climate and nature concern increase satisfaction from joining due to alignment with environmental values; economic insecurity reduces satisfaction from joining, reflecting perceived risks (e.g., time, job security) and a need to prioritize personal stability; and pro-growth attitudes generate dissonance with environmental activism, thus lowering satisfaction from joining and increasing it for not joining. Conformity satisfaction is derived from the agent’s social network. Agents feel more satisfied when they do what most of their peers are doing.

These satisfaction values are drawn from normal distributions, scaled by each motive’s importance. Table 2 presents the mean values and their rationale for both joining and not joining.

Motive Type	eNGO Membership		Action Protest		Disruptive Action Protest	
	Join: N(μ , σ)	Not Join: N(μ , σ)	Join: N(μ , σ)	Not Join: N(μ , σ)	Join: N(μ , σ)	Not Join: N(μ , σ)
Climate Concern	N(0.4, 0.05)	N(-0.2, 0.05)	N(0.5, 0.05)	N(-0.3, 0.05)	N(0.2, 0.05)	N(-0.1, 0.05)
Nature Concern	N(0.5, 0.05)	N(-0.4, 0.05)	N(0.6, 0.05)	N(-0.4, 0.05)	N(0.3, 0.05)	N(-0.2, 0.05)
Economic Security	N(-0.5, 0.05)	N(0.3, 0.05)	N(-0.2, 0.05)	N(0.2, 0.05)	N(-0.5, 0.05)	N(0.4, 0.05)
Growth-First Belief	N(-0.6, 0.05)	N(0.4, 0.05)	N(-0.7, 0.05)	N(0.5, 0.05)	N(-0.8, 0.05)	N(0.6, 0.05)
Conformity	Satisfaction = $2P-1$	Satisfaction = $1-2P$	Satisfaction = $2P-1$	Satisfaction = $1-2P$	Satisfaction = $2P-1$	Satisfaction = $1-2P$

Table 2. Satisfaction Distributions by Motive and Decision Type. Satisfaction values are sampled from normal distributions with means (μ) and standard deviations ($\sigma = 0.05$). Distributions reflect the relative satisfaction (or dissatisfaction) expected when an agent chooses to join or not join, conditional on each motive and decision type. P represents the proportion of the agent’s peers who have already joined an eNGO.

6.4.3 OA Variables: Opportunities and Abilities

In addition to internal motivations, an agent’s satisfaction to join an eNGO may increase depending on whether they have the opportunity (O) and ability (A) to act. To capture this, we identify four questions from the NCP survey that serve as proxies for opportunity and ability (e.g. time availability, confidence in the political system, prior civic engagement). Additionally, eNGO presence, determines whether the action is available at all (Table 3).

OA variable	Role	NCP Source	What it represents
eNGO Present	Opportunity	— (simulation input)	An existing eNGO group
Political Self-Efficacy	Ability	“How confident are you in your own abilities to participate in politics?”	Agent’s confidence in their ability to engage politically
System Responsiveness	Opportunity	“To what extent does the political system in Norway give people like you influence?”.	Agent’s perception of whether the political system responds to them
Civic Engagement	Opportunity	'Are you an active member of any of the following types of associations/organizations?’	Prior engagement in civic/political actions (e.g., voting, petitions)
Employment Status	Opportunity	“Which of the following descriptions best applies to what you have been doing for the last seven days?”	Time availability and competing priorities (e.g., work)

Table 3. Mapping of OA variables affecting the eNGO Decision.

Responses to these questions (OA modifiers) can adjust the satisfaction levels associated with joining (or not) an eNGO, but only under the climate concern and nature concern motives (Table 2). These are the only motives for which joining an NGO produces a positive satisfaction, i.e., where the action of joining aligns with the motive. Here, alignment means that the model defines the action as theoretically satisfying the motive. However, the actual satisfaction an agent experiences from joining depends not only on this alignment but also on how important that motive is to the agent. If the agent assigns a motive zero importance, then the resulting satisfaction is zero—regardless of how well the action theoretically satisfies it. OA variables therefore only affect agents for whom the action is both meaningful and motivationally relevant. They do not push agents toward the action, but rather amplify the satisfaction from joining when (and only when) the agent assigns non-zero importance to a motive that the action supports (Table 4).

OA Variable	Response Level	Interpretation	Effect on satisfaction (join)	Effect on satisfaction (not join)
Political Self-Efficacy	Low (0–3)	“I can’t do this”	+0.00	-0.00
	Medium (4–7)	“I could, maybe”	+0.05	-0.05
	High (8–10)	“I’m capable”	+0.10	-0.10
System Responsiveness	Low (0–3)	“It’s pointless”	+0.00	-0.00
	Medium (4–7)	“Maybe it works”	+0.05	-0.05
	High (8–10)	“My action matters”	+0.10	-0.10
Civic Engagement	0–1 actions	Not engaged	+0.00	-0.00
	2–3 actions	Moderately engaged	+0.05	-0.05
	4–5+ actions	Highly engaged	+0.1	-0.10
Employment Status	Full-time	High time cost, low flexibility	+0.00	-0.00
	Part-time / student	Some flexibility	+0.05	-0.05
	Other	High availability	+0.10	-0.10

Table 4. OA variables and their effect on satisfaction levels.

These decision rules allow the model to represent realistic variation in who becomes active in environmental movements and under what conditions. The interaction of motives, structural constraints, and social influence enables nuanced patterns of citizen mobilization to emerge over time.

6.5 Participating in an Action

The second behavioral decision modeled is whether a citizen chooses to participate in an action (e.g., a protest, boycott, information campaign). The term ‘action’ here can have a wide range of meanings depending on the context and environmental issue addressed, and may be adapted in subsequent steps of modelling according to the focus of each LL. In the literature on environmental protest, ‘action’ may refer to a range of radical protest forms, e.g. ‘climate actions involving property damage, such as arson, slashing SUV tires, and sabotaging pipelines’ (Jansma et al. 2025), but in the Kildn case we operationalized actions to include any active campaigning to conserve the area under threat of development. In LLs where protest is not involved at all, it may be operationalized quite differently. And if ENGOS play no role in the LL, we can weight their influence to zero.

This decision applies to all citizens, regardless of eNGO membership. Like the eNGO decision, this behavior is simulated using the HUMAT-MOA framework and is empirically grounded in the 2023–2024 waves of the Norwegian Citizen Panel (NCP).

Each agent evaluates the satisfaction they would derive from either participating in or abstaining from protest, based on the importance of several motives. These motives are identical to those used in the eNGO membership decision and include climate concern, nature concern, economic security, and growth-first belief (Table 1). The social motive of conformity is also included and, as previously

explained, its importance is not derived from survey data but is set as a scenario parameter, based on cultural assumptions (Gelfand et al., 2011).

6.5.1 Satisfaction Values for Joining or Not Joining an Action

Although the motives are the same, the satisfaction values associated with this decision differ. This reflects the distinct nature of protest behavior, the form of action modelled in this case — typically more public, less time-sensitive, and confrontational than eNGO membership. For example, while economic insecurity discouraged joining an eNGO due to long-term commitments, it may discourage protest participation even more due to its immediate risks. Satisfaction values are drawn from normal distributions (Table 2). As before, conformity satisfaction is calculated dynamically based on the proportion of peers who have participated in a protest (P).

6.5.2 OA Variables: Opportunities and Abilities

As in the eNGO decision, action participation depends not only on an agent's motivations but also on whether they have the opportunity and ability to act. The same set of OA variables is used here—political self-efficacy, system responsiveness, civic engagement, and employment status—all derived from NCP questions. These variables are applied only when the satisfaction for a given motive is positive and adjust satisfaction by the same amounts described in Table 4 of Section 5.4.

In addition, action participation includes one extra condition: the agent must be aware that an action (in this case protest) is taking place. If they have not heard about any protest, participation is not possible regardless of motivation or other factors.

6.6 Participating in a Disruptive Action Protest

The third behavioral decision modeled is whether a citizen joins a disruptive environmental protest. This decision, like the previous ones, is modeled using the HUMAT-MOA framework and is empirically grounded in the 2023–2024 waves of the Norwegian Citizen Panel (NCP). Disruptive protest involves higher personal and social risk than conventional protest, requiring a more selective and restrictive decision logic.

6.6.1 Motives and Their Empirical Mapping

The motives used in this decision are identical to those used for eNGO membership and general protest participation. These include climate concern, nature concern, economic security, growth-first belief, and the social motive of conformity. Each is derived from NCP questions and translated into an importance value ranging from 0 to 1, as described in Table 1 of Section 5.4. The importance of conformity is again defined as a scenario parameter based on cultural assumptions (Gelfand et al., 2011).

6.6.2 Satisfaction Values for Joining or not Joining in a Disruptive Action Protest

Although the motives are the same, the satisfaction values differ to reflect the more confrontational nature of disruptive protest. Participation is riskier, more visible, and often norm-defying, which increases the psychological cost for many agents. At the same time, it can generate higher moral satisfaction for strongly committed individuals (Table 2).

6.6.3 OA Variables: Opportunities and Abilities

The decision to join a disruptive protest is also conditioned by the same OA variables as previous decisions: political self-efficacy, system responsiveness, civic engagement, and employment status. These are derived from the same NCP items and apply in the same way as described in Section 5.4, Tables 3 and 4. In addition, two specific constraints apply in this decision:

1. Awareness of a disruptive protest: Agents must have heard about an upcoming disruptive protest to be eligible. If not, participation is not possible.
2. Activist alignment filter: OA modifiers are only applied to agents classified as Engaged Sympathizers. This classification is based on how agents respond to four NCP items related

to public perceptions of disruptive climate activism, each introduced by the prompt: “*Lately, there have been some media stories about climate activists throwing paint at artwork, gluing themselves to buildings, or stopping traffic*”. Respondents rate their agreement with each item on a 0–6 scale, where 0 means completely disagree and 6 means completely agree.

The four items are:

- a) “I sympathize with the climate activists”
- b) “I am proud of the climate activists”
- c) “I think such activism is not good for the climate cause”
- d) “I think such climate activism is ridiculous”

Two scores are calculated:

- Support Score = mean of a and b
- Disapproval Score = mean of the c and d

Agents are then categorized as follows:

- Engaged Sympathizers: Agents with a Support Score ≥ 4.0 and a Disapproval Score ≥ 4.0 . These individuals express strong approval of both climate activists and their tactics, indicating a high degree of emotional and normative alignment.
- Conflicted Supporters: Agents with a Support Score ≥ 4.0 but a Disapproval Score < 4.0 . They support the activists but disapprove of the disruptive methods used, suggesting mixed alignment.
- Detached Observers: Agents with a Support Score < 4.0 and a Disapproval Score ≥ 4.0 . These individuals are generally neutral or emotionally disengaged from both the activists and their tactics.
- Outright Opponents: Agents with a Support Score < 4.0 and a Disapproval Score < 4.0 . They reject both the activists and their methods, showing clear opposition.
- Unclassified: Agents with missing or incomplete data for any of the four relevant items. These are treated as neutral for modeling purposes.

Only agents classified as Engaged Sympathizers are eligible to receive satisfaction modifiers from OA variables (Table 4) in the disruptive protest decision.

7. Institutional Agents and Decision-Making Algorithms

In addition to citizens, the PRO-CLIMATE model includes several institutional and organizational agents that shape the decision environment. These include media organizations, environmental NGOs (eNGOs), politicians, and urban planners. Each of these agents is modeled with its own behavioral logic, data-informed parameters, and interaction pathways with the rest of the system.

This section describes the behavior and decision-making algorithms of each institutional agent. Politicians are included here for structural clarity, although they may also be considered a separate category of actors due to their hybrid individual-institutional role.

7.1 Media Agent Behavior

In the PRO-CLIMATE model, a media agent simulates institutional news outlets such as newspapers, radio stations, and television networks. This agent operates continuously and influence the model through both the generation of news and its propagation through media and social media channels. Media shapes public discourse by modulating the importance of the motives in citizens, ultimately thus affecting their decisions.

7.1.1 News Generation and Delivery

At each time step, there is a probabilistic chance that a media agent will generate a news item. The type and ideological direction of the news is determined stochastically:

- *newsFrequency* controls the probability probability that a news item is is generated (e.g., 0.6).
- *proNewsRatio* determines the likelihood that the new will be pro-environment rather than pro-economic (e.g., 0.5).
- *socialShareProb* sets the probability that a media article is also shared via social media (e.g., 0.6).

News is delivered through two primary channels:

- Institutional media (e.g., tv, radio, newspapers) is the default channel and all news are delivered via this channel.
- Social media, publication via this channel is probabilistic and based on *socialShareProb* parameter.

This delivery logic reflects the hybrid nature of modern information ecosystems, where mainstream media content is frequently echoed and amplified through digital platforms.

7.1.2 Impact on Citizen Motives

The direction of the news affects which motives are amplified in citizens:

- Pro-environment news increases the importance of motives such as *climate concern* and *nature concern*.
- Pro-economic news increases the importance of motives like *economic security* and *growth-first orientation*.

The adjustment in motive importance is computed using a logistic sensitivity function that reflects realistic cognitive dynamics. This ensures that media effects are strongest at moderate levels of concern and weaker at low or high levels.

7.1.3 Media Exposure Probability

Not all citizens are equally likely to encounter media content. In the model, exposure probabilities are derived from the following question in the Norwegian Citizen Panel:

“Where do you usually look for information about politics and news? Select all that you use.”

- TV
- Radio
- Newspapers (also online)
- Social Media
- Other online sources
- Family/Friends
- At work/study
- None of the options
- Do not wish to answer
- NA

Based on responses, agents are classified into two information types:

- Media Consumers: Selected one or more of TV, Radio, Newspapers
- Social Consumers: Selected Social Media or Other online sources

The number of sources selected within each type determines the agent’s probability of exposure to media content delivered through that channel (Table 5).

News Channel	Response Condition	Probability of Exposure
Institutional Media	Yes to TV, Radio, and Newspapers	0.8
	Yes to any two of TV, Radio, Newspapers	0.6
	Yes to only one of TV, Radio, Newspapers	0.5
	Yes to other options (e.g., Family/Friends, Work/Study), but not media sources	0.3
	No to all, or selected “Do not wish to answer” / NA	0.1
Social Media	Yes to both Social Media and Other Online Sources	0.8
	Yes to only one of Social Media or Other Online	0.6
	Yes to other options (e.g., Family/Friends, Work/Study), but not social sources	0.3
	No to all, or selected “Do not wish to answer” / NA	0.1

Table 5. Probability of Exposure to News Based on Media Use.

7.2 Environmental NGOs and Activist Behavior

Environmental NGOs (eNGOs) play a key role in the PRO-CLIMATE model by introducing political pressure, public messaging, and tactical disruptions that shape the decisions of citizens and policymakers alike. To model eNGO behavior in a realistic yet tractable way, we conducted a comprehensive literature review, drawing on empirical studies by Dalton (2003), Carmin & Baiser (2002), Berny & Rootes (2018), and Can & Gonenc (2024). These works identify a wide range of eNGO activities and the structural and cognitive factors shaping their strategic repertoires.

7.2.1 Literature-Derived Typology of eNGO Actions

The review identifies four major dimensions of eNGO political activity, first synthesized by Dalton (2003) through cluster analysis of data from over 50 countries:

- Conventional Activities: Lobbying, litigation, participation in advisory boards, and collaboration with government actors.
- Mobilizing Activities: Public awareness campaigns and grassroots organizing to shape public opinion.
- Protest Activities: Demonstrations, direct actions, and symbolic disruptions.
- Networking Activities: Alliance-building with other NGOs or social movements, including cross-sector collaboration.

Additional actions such as indirect support for radical flanks and symbolic cultural protest (e.g., Greenpeace ship confrontations) were also identified but often overlap with these core dimensions.

7.2.2 Model Simplification: Four Strategic Categories

We collapsed the full repertoire into four modelled action types, each representing a cluster of similar strategies:

- Direct Actions – lobbying, litigation, and formal engagement with institutions.
- Indirect Actions – awareness and public media campaigns.
- Action Protest – conventional street protest and demonstrations.
- Disruptive Action Protest – high-impact actions such as blockades, unauthorized disruptions, and radical symbolism.

This structure preserves the empirical diversity of eNGO tactics while streamlining them into a set of distinct algorithmic choices agents can make within the simulation (Fig 5).

Figure 5. eNGO attributes, actions and outcomes

7.2.3 eNGO Attributes

Across the literature, a consistent set of factors has been identified as shaping which actions eNGOs are likely to consider and pursue. While individual studies vary slightly in terminology or emphasis, they converge on five core attributes that influence organizational strategy: resources, experience, strategic orientation, cultural trust¹, and political system (Beryn & Rootes, 2018; Can & Gonenc,

¹ *Cultural trust* subsumes closely related notions such as social trust in democratic norms (Dalton 2003), internal legitimacy (Carmin & Baiser 2002), and legitimacy of activism within a society's cultural context (Beryn & Rootes 2018; Can & Gonenc 2024). In the model it serves two roles: (i) setting thresholds for action eligibility and (ii) weighting action intensity (see following sections for details).

2024; Carmin & Balsler, 2002; Dalton et al., 2003). In the model, these attributes are implemented as internal eNGO variables that modulate the likelihood of selecting specific action types.

1. Resources [0–1]: eNGOs with more financial and organizational capacity (e.g., staff, infrastructure) are better equipped to carry out costly or complex actions such as litigation or media campaigns.
2. Experience (0+ years): Organizational maturity—reflected in group age or accumulated strategic knowledge—tends to foster the use of more stable, institutionalized action repertoires.
3. Strategic Orientation [0–1]: This dimension reflects whether an eNGO is generally collaborative (with 0 max collaborative) or confrontational (1 max confrontational).
4. Cultural Trust [0–1]: Confidence that advocacy and protest will be viewed as legitimate and effective in the prevailing social and institutional culture. Higher values favour institutional engagement; lower values tilt toward contentious tactics.
5. Political System: The openness of the political system sets structural limits on which strategies are available or likely to succeed. While this factor is emphasized in cross-national studies, in our model we assume a politically open system, consistent with our focus on democratic urban governance settings (e.g., the Vestland case). As such, all action types are considered available, and variation in behaviour arises from organizational rather than systemic constraints.

Together, these attributes allow the model to represent heterogeneous strategic profiles among eNGO agents, reflecting both internal capacities and external environments. This variability supports emergent patterns of interaction and influence within the broader decision system.

We now describe each action in detail, including its theoretical basis, modelling rationale, and systemic effects. The eligibility thresholds applied in these action algorithms are based on expert-informed insights and chosen for plausibility. They are not definitive and will be refined in collaboration with stakeholders during future model calibration efforts.

7.2.4 eNGO Direct Actions: Institutional Engagement

Direct actions include institutional strategies such as lobbying, litigation, and collaboration with government bodies (e.g., participation in commissions). These actions aim to influence policy and decision-makers within the established political framework (Berny & Rootes, 2018; Can & Gonenc, 2024; Carmin & Balsler, 2002; Dalton et al., 2003).

Action Eligibility

In the model, not all eNGOs are eligible to engage in direct institutional actions. These include activities such as lobbying, legal challenges, or participation in formal consultation processes. Because these actions demand capacity, trust, and institutional access, eligibility is determined by a combination of internal organizational attributes and external context, as consistently emphasized in the literature.

The five conditions required for direct action eligibility are as follows:

- Political System: Must be classified as open, allowing institutional engagement.
- Cultural Trust: Must be ≥ 0.5 , representing confidence in the legitimacy and responsiveness of institutions.
- Resources: Must be ≥ 0.6 , reflecting the financial and organizational capacity to carry out formal actions.
- Experience (in years): Must be ≥ 3 , as institutional navigation often requires accumulated knowledge and procedural familiarity.
- Strategy: If ≤ 0.3 , the eNGO is treated as explicitly collaborative and fully eligible. If > 0.3 , the action is still possible, but the probability of selection is scaled by $1 - \text{Strategy}$, meaning more confrontational organizations are less likely to choose institutional strategies.

These conditions are used to filter the pool of eligible actions. However, meeting them does not automatically result in direct action. Final selection is determined by a probabilistic mechanism that is further calibrated using empirical case study data.

Action Intensity

When an eNGO performs a direct action, its intensity determines how influential that action is within the political decision space. Intensity is calculated using a weighted combination of three internal attributes:

$$\text{Intensity} = 10 \times \text{Resources} + 8 \times \text{Experience} + 5 \times \text{Cultural Trust}$$

These weights reflect the relative importance of each attribute:

- Resources capture the eNGO's capacity to implement the action effectively.
- Experience contributes to the credibility and professionalization of the effort.
- Cultural Trust enhances the perceived legitimacy of the action by decision-makers.

The resulting intensity score is used to modulate the eNGO's influence in the simulation.

Cumulative Intensity and Diminishing Returns

If multiple direct actions are taken over time, their cumulative effect is not linear. The model implements a diminishing returns function, where each successive action contributes less to the total perceived pressure than the previous one. This reflects real-world dynamics, where repeated lobbying or litigation may lose marginal effectiveness due to saturation, institutional fatigue, or political adaptation.

This cumulative intensity value becomes one of the inputs influencing political decision-making in the model (see Section 5.3 on Politicians).

7.2.5 eNGO Indirect Actions: Public Awareness and Information Campaigns

Indirect actions refer to strategies used by eNGOs to shape public opinion, raise awareness, or shift the public narrative.

Action Eligibility

Indirect actions are broadly accessible in the model and are governed by a single organizational attribute: resources. Other attributes—such as strategy, experience, or cultural trust—do not constrain access to this action type. This reflects the relatively low institutional barriers and wide applicability of public awareness efforts.

To qualify, an eNGO must have at least minimal resources (≥ 0.1) to produce and disseminate outreach, including low-cost campaigns via social media platforms (e.g., Facebook, Instagram, online videos). These channels are accessible to nearly all eNGOs, enabling even smaller or less professionalized organizations to participate in public discourse.

In contrast, access to conventional media (e.g., television, radio, newspapers) requires significantly more capacity. eNGOs must have resources ≥ 0.6 to be eligible. Even then, coverage is not guaranteed: the probability of securing conventional media exposure increases linearly with available resources, reflecting real-world conditions where greater capacity boosts visibility but does not ensure it.

Information Dissemination and Public Impact

When an indirect action is triggered, it results in the creation of one or more news items, which are broadcast through the channel(s) available to the eNGO. Messages disseminated via social media are available to all eligible eNGOs, while conventional media broadcasts are limited to those with sufficient resources.

These news items are only seen by agents who actively follow the corresponding media channel, allowing for targeted influence. Not all citizens are equally likely to be exposed. When exposure does occur, the message may alter the importance of the citizen's internal motives, such as increasing concern for climate or economic issues depending on the content (see Section 6.1).

7.2.6 eNGO Protest Actions

Protest actions include public demonstrations, marches, sit-ins, and other visible confrontational tactics aimed at pressuring decision-makers and mobilizing the public.

Action Eligibility

Unlike direct institutional strategies, protest actions do not require trust in institutions or extensive organizational maturity. This reflects the fact that protest can be a low-barrier, high-visibility tactic used even by newly formed or marginal groups—particularly in open democratic systems.

In the model, the following conditions must be met for an eNGO to be eligible to engage in protest actions:

- Political System: Must be open (protests are not modeled in autocratic or repressive settings).
- Resources: Must be ≥ 0.2 , representing the minimal financial and organizational capacity required to coordinate a public demonstration.
- Strategy: If ≥ 0.5 , the eNGO is treated as confrontational and fully eligible. If < 0.5 , the action is still possible, but with probability scaled by the strategy value itself, i.e., the more collaborative an eNGO is (i.e., lower strategy score), the less likely to engage in protests.

Meeting these criteria makes an eNGO eligible for protest, though actual selection is governed by a probabilistic mechanism calibrated to empirical case data.

Action Intensity

The effectiveness or visibility of a protest action is a function of three elements:

Intensity = $5 \times \text{Resources} + 5 \times \text{Experience} + 10 \times \text{Protest Size}$

- Resources (R) and Experience (E) reflect the organizational capacity to plan, coordinate, and execute a protest effectively.
- Protest Size (S)—expressed as a proportion of the population—is the strongest determinant of protest impact.

This weighted formula reflects that while capacity is important, the number of participants drives public and political response more directly than back-end planning.

Cumulative Intensity and Diminishing Returns

As with direct actions, repeated protest activities do not yield linear gains in influence. The model uses a diminishing returns function to accumulate protest effects over time. The first few protests may significantly increase visibility and pressure, but subsequent ones yield progressively less additional impact.

This cumulative effect becomes one of the inputs into the political decision-making algorithms (see Section 7.3 on Politicians).

7.2.7 eNGO Disruptive Protest Actions

Disruptive protest actions include radical and high-risk tactics such as blockades, obstruction, defacement, and other nonviolent but norm-violating behaviors aimed at forcing political or public attention. These are typically used when other strategies fail or when urgency and moral outrage override concerns about public or institutional backlash.

Action Eligibility

Disruptive protests are intentionally modeled as extreme behaviors that only a subset of eNGOs can consider. Unlike direct or conventional protest actions, they are not conditioned on institutional trust, political openness, or organizational maturity. This reflects real-world dynamics where disruptive tactics are often used by newer, more radical groups or in moments of perceived crisis.

The eligibility conditions include only the following internal organizational variables:

- Resources ≥ 0.2 : The ENGO must have basic financial and organizational capacity to plan and execute disruptive events.
- Strategy: If ≥ 0.8 , the ENGO is fully eligible. If < 0.8 , the action is still possible, but the probability decreases linearly with lower strategy values, i.e., the more collaborative an eNGO, the less likely to pursue disruptive protest.

Meeting these criteria grants eligibility, but actual selection is probabilistic and further tuned using empirical data.

Action Intensity

The intensity of a disruptive protest is determined using the same weighted structure as other protest types, with particular emphasis on participation size due to its outsized impact on media coverage and public perception:

Intensity = $5 \times \text{Resources} + 5 \times \text{Experience} + 10 \times \text{Protest Size}$

Cumulative Intensity and Diminishing Returns

Disruptive protest intensity is accumulated over time using a diminishing returns function. The first major disruptive action tends to generate a strong impact, but repeated uses yield smaller marginal influence. This cumulative intensity is a key input into the decision-making of political agents (see Section 7.3 on Politicians).

7.3 Politicians: Decision-Making Algorithms

In the PRO-CLIMATE model, politicians represent key decision-makers who ultimately determine the fate of infrastructure proposals within the simulation. Their primary function is to evaluate and either approve, reject, or demand modifications to these proposals based on a combination of public signals, institutional feedback, and internal strategic priorities.

Rather than acting as purely rational optimizers or rigid ideologues, politicians are modeled as boundedly rational agents who seek to balance multiple goals: retaining public support, promoting preferred policies, and maintaining or enhancing their position within the political system. Their decisions are shaped by dynamic inputs from the simulation environment—including citizen sentiment, urban planner assessments, eNGO and protest activity, and media tone—as well as internal party cues and peer alignment. Politicians thus serve as a crucial bridge between public opinion, institutional expertise, and political outcomes.

7.3.1 Decision Process Overview

The political decision-making process unfolds in two main stages: an initial external evaluation of the proposal, followed by internal negotiation with peers and party colleagues (Fig 6).

Figure 6. Politician Decision-Making Process

Stage 1 – External Input Aggregation

Politicians begin by gathering and integrating a set of inputs from their environment:

- Proposal Revisions by Urban Planners and other institutions [0-1]: A score of the technical assessments of the proposal: 0 negative; 0.5 neutral; and 1 positive evaluation.
- Media Tone [-1,1]: A composite score representing the overall tone of media coverage, ranging from -1 (strongly negative) to +1 (strongly positive).
- Society [0-1]: A measure of citizen sentiment, based on the proportion of people in favor or against the proposal.
- eNGO Pressure [-1,1]: A value derived from accumulated eNGO direct actions.
- Personal Stance [-1,1]: The politician’s own predefined position on development vs sustainability.
- Party Stance [-1,1]: The average position of their political party on development vs sustainability.

These signals collectively represent the technical, social, and political climate surrounding the proposal. They are normalized, weighted, and aggregated into a single external evaluation score that serves as the politician’s preliminary judgment of the proposal.

Stage 2 – Internal Peer/Party Adjustment

After forming an initial judgment based on external inputs, each politician adjusts their decision by comparing it to those of their peers and party colleagues. This stage captures intra-party negotiation, peer pressure, and party discipline, simulating how local political dynamics influence individual decisions. The adjustment is based on a peer signal that weighs the decisions of other politicians giving greater influence to peers of the same party or with similar party orientations.

7.3.2 Strategic Orientation

Each politician in the model is characterized by a strategic orientation—a set of internal weights that define how much importance they place on different political goals. These orientations shape how politicians interpret external signals and how they respond during internal negotiations.

Based on the theory of political party competition (Strom, 1990), the model incorporates three classic political goals:

- **Vote-Seeking:** acting in line with what is likely to gain voter approval and maximize electoral support.
- **Policy-Seeking:** prioritizing alignment with personal or ideological policy goals, regardless of electoral consequences.
- **Office-Seeking:** behaving to maintain or gain a position of political authority, often balancing party loyalty, rules, and visibility.

Each political strategy affects how much weight a politician assigns to different sources of input during Stage 1 of the decision-making process. For instance, a politician with a strong vote-seeking orientation will place more emphasis on public sentiment, while a policy-seeker will prioritize internal consistency with their party or personal stance.

To operationalize this, each strategy defines a qualitative priority level—low, moderate, or high—for each type of input. These levels are then used to adjust the default weight of that input accordingly:

- Low priority → weight is decreased
- Moderate priority → weight remains unchanged
- High priority → weight is increased

This allows each politician’s strategic profile to shape how they interpret the environment before any peer or party adjustment occurs (Table 6).

Input	Vote-seeking	Policy-Seeking	Office-Seeking
Urban Planner	Low	High	Moderate
eNGO	Low	High	Low
Society	High	Low	High
Media	High	Low	High
Personal Stance	Low	High	Moderate
Party Stance	Moderate	Moderate	High

Table 6. Priority Levels Assigned to Each Input by Political Strategy. Each politician’s strategic orientation (vote-, policy-, or office-seeking) determines how much they prioritize each source of input during external signal aggregation. Priority levels adjust the default weights by increasing, maintaining, or decreasing their influence.

These strategic orientations are internal attributes of politicians and do not change during the simulation. However, they play a key role in how external evaluations are interpreted and how final decisions are formed in conjunction with peer adjustments.

7.3.3 Stage 1 Decision Rule

In Stage 1, each politician computes a preliminary decision about the proposal by aggregating the external inputs into two utility scores:

- **Utility_accept:** How strongly they support accepting the proposal
- **Utility_reject:** How strongly they support rejecting the proposal

Each score is computed from the six inputs described previously. The inputs are first transformed and then weighted according to a set of principles described below.

Step 1: Input Transformations

Each input is converted into a form that reflects both its direction (support vs. opposition) and its strength.

Urban Planners Input ($U_1, U_2, U_3, \dots, U_n$)

These inputs represent the technical assessments of the proposal made by different government institutions (e.g., city council) or other groups (e.g., eNGO or public consultation groups). Each U is centered at 0.5 (neutral), then modulated by the Expert Framing Level (EFL), which reduces its influence if the issue is already pre-framed:

$$U_i = (U_i - 0.5) * (1 - EFL)$$

If $U_i > 0$: Planners support the proposal, $U_i < 0$: Planners are against it.

Society (S) and Media (M) Inputs

Society and media inputs represent the share of the population or media content that supports the proposal. Both values are expressed as proportions within the range [0, 1], where 1 indicates full support and 0 indicates full opposition.

The society signal (S) is calculated based on protest activity. It captures the proportion of the population that is not actively opposing the proposal:

$$S = 1 - (P_s + DP_s * (1 - \rho))$$

Where:

- P_s : Proportion of the commune participating in regular protests
- DP_s : Proportion participating in disruptive protests
- ρ : Proportion of the population that rejects disruptive protest (i.e., views it negatively)

This formula accounts for both the level of mobilization and the public's reaction to more extreme tactics. If disruptive protests are widely rejected, they reduce support more strongly—capturing dynamics like backlash or erosion of legitimacy.

The media signal (M) is calculated as the proportion of news items in favor of the proposal out of all news items related to it. A value of 1 means all coverage is supportive, 0.5 indicates a neutral or evenly split tone, and 0 means all coverage is negative.

To reflect the strength and direction of support, both the society signal (S) and media tone (M) are transformed using a log-ratio, followed by a *tanh* normalization:

$$S_t = \tanh \left(\log \left(\frac{S + \epsilon}{1 - S + \epsilon} \right) \right)$$

Where:

- ϵ is a small constant (e.g., 0.01) to prevent division by zero

This transformation does the following:

- Captures whether the signal favors acceptance (> 0) or rejection (< 0)
- Amplifies strong majorities (e.g., 70% support \approx strong positive signal)
- Dampens influence near parity (e.g., 51% vs. 49% \approx near-neutral)
- Keeps values within a bounded range (-1 to $+1$), simplifying downstream calculations

Overall, this reflects the idea that political pressure grows disproportionately when clear public or media majorities emerge, while weak or divided opinions exert minimal force.

NGO Pressure (D), Personal Stance (P), and Party Stance (PP) Inputs

Environmental NGOs, individual politicians, and political parties may support or oppose a given proposal. These inputs are represented on a scale from -1 to +1, where:

- +1 indicates strong support,
- -1 indicates strong opposition,
- 0 is neutral.

To integrate these inputs into the utility functions, each value is split into its supportive and opposing components, depending on its sign. The logic is as follows:

- If the input is positive, it contributes only to acceptance.
- If the input is negative, its absolute value contributes only to rejection.

For example:

- If $D = 0.5$, then $D_{\text{accept}} = 0.5$, $D_{\text{reject}} = 0$
- If $D = -0.3$, then $D_{\text{accept}} = 0$, $D_{\text{reject}} = 0.3$

The same rule applies to Personal Stance (P) and Party Stance (PP).

This directional split ensures that each input contributes only to the side it supports, allowing the model to distinguish between active opposition and passive neutrality.

Table 7 provides a summary example, illustrating how raw input values are transformed and split before contributing to the two utility functions—one favoring acceptance, the other favoring rejection. It shows both the intermediate transformations (e.g., log-ratio normalization or directional splitting) and the resulting effects on the decision process.

Input	Raw Value	Transformed	Effect on Accept	Effect on Reject
U	0.8	$U = +0.15$	+0.15 (boosts)	-0.15 (hurts)
S	0.3	$S = -0.69$	-0.69 (hurts)	+0.69 (boosts)
D	-0.7	$D_{\text{reject}} = 0.7$	0 (neutral)	+0.7 (boosts)
M	0.3	$M = -0.69$	-0.69 (hurts)	+0.69 (boosts)
P	+0.8	$P_{\text{accept}} = 0.8$	0.8 (boosts)	0 (neutral)
PP	+0.6	$PP_{\text{accept}} = 0.6$	0.6 (boosts)	0 (neutral)

Table 7. Example of Input values and their effects on acceptance/rejection of a proposal

Step 2: Weight Calculations

Once all external inputs have been transformed (as detailed in Step 1), the next step is to determine how much influence each of them should have on the politician’s decision. This is done through a weighted aggregation. Every input has an associated baseline weight, which reflects its typical importance across all decisions (Table 8).

Input	Symbol	Baseline Weight	Rationale
Urban Planner	WU	0.33 (U1, U2, U3 → 0.11 each)	Authoritative but procedural input. Their influence is always relevant but typically limited at the decision stage—especially if the issue has already been framed.
NGO Pressure	WD	0.11	NGOs exert structured advocacy pressure, often grounded in expertise or activism. Their influence is significant but tends to target specific causes.

Society Feedback	WS	0.17	Citizens' views can have strong political implications—especially during high-salience events. This weight is modulated by salience.
Media Tone	WM	0.17	Media strongly influences public sentiment and elite attention, especially when coverage is extensive. Like society, it is modulated by salience.
Personal Stance	WP	0.11	The politician's own values play a consistent but bounded role. They rarely override strategic or institutional inputs
Party Stance	WPP	0.11	Party lines guide decisions, especially for elected officials, but some autonomy remains—particularly at the local level.

Table 8. Baseline weights and their meaning

The total of all baseline weights is 1.0, ensuring all influence is properly normalized. These weights should not be interpreted as absolute empirical values, but rather as relative influence levels across input sources. Their purpose is to define the balance of power among different actors in the decision-making process, not to represent measurable quantities. For instance, the difference between weights of 0.11 and 0.17 does not imply a strict numerical gap in real-world influence, but signals that society and media inputs are generally more impactful—especially when salience is high. The weights are therefore designed to reflect plausible and defensible differentials, informed by stakeholder knowledge and literature, and can be modified in future calibrations.

Salience Scaling for Society (S) and Media (M)

Inputs from society and media can vary in visibility depending on the issue. To model this, their baseline weights are multiplied by a salience score:

$$WS_{adj} = W_S * Sal_S \quad \text{and} \quad WM_{adj} = W_M * Sal_M$$

Where:

- WS, WM = baseline weights for society and media (Table 8)
- $Sal_S, Sal_M \in [0,1]$ = normalized salience scores
- If salience = 0, the channel has no influence
- If salience = 1, the channel gets its full baseline weight

Salience is computed as the ratio of observed activity to a theoretical maximum (informed by empirical data). For the society input, salience is determined by dividing the total number of protests observed in the model by a theoretical maximum number of protests, which reflects high-mobilization scenarios drawn from real-world cases. For the media input, salience is calculated as the number of news items generated in the model divided by the expected maximum coverage in a highly publicized case. This approach ensures that salience remains anchored in realistic reference points and allows the model to distinguish between low-profile proposals and those that are socially or politically prominent.

Hence, when salience is low—for example, due to limited protest activity or sparse media coverage—politicians are likely to perceive these signals as politically irrelevant or muted, and thus assign them less influence. In contrast, high salience—such as in situations of mass mobilization or extensive media attention—signals to politicians that these inputs are politically consequential. Accordingly, society and media feedback become more heavily weighted in the decision process when public visibility is high.

Strategy-Based Weight Modulation

As introduced in Section 7.3.2, each politician is characterized by a strategic orientation—vote-seeking, policy-seeking, or office-seeking—which defines how much weight they place on different political goals.

To implement this, every strategy assigns a qualitative priority level—low, moderate, or high—to each input type. These priority levels are then translated into numerical multipliers that adjust the input's baseline weight:

- Low priority: the baseline weight is reduced by dividing it by a constant m
- Moderate priority: the weight remains unchanged
- High priority: the weight is increased by multiplying it by m

For example, a vote-seeking politician gives high priority to media and society signals, so their weights are amplified, while planner input or NGO pressure may be reduced due to low priority. The result is that different politicians interpret the same external signals in different ways, depending on their political strategy.

For inputs like Society (S) and Media (M), this strategy-based multiplier is combined with the salience score described earlier. In these cases, the total adjusted weight is:

$$W_i^{adj} = W_i * m_i * Sal_i$$

Where:

- W_i : the input's baseline weight
- m_i : the multiplier corresponding to its strategic priority
- Sal_i : the normalized salience score (for S and M only)

For all other inputs only the strategy-based multiplier m_i applied:

$$W_i^{adj} = W_i * m_i$$

Final Weight Normalization

After applying these adjustments, the total weight across all inputs may no longer sum to 1. To ensure consistency, all adjusted weights are normalized by dividing each one by the total sum of all adjusted weights.

Let:

$$W_{total} = \sum_i W_i^{adj}$$

Then:

$$W_i^{final} = \frac{W_i^{adj}}{W_{total}}$$

This final normalization guarantees that the full set of weights behaves like a proper probability distribution, with relative importance preserved but scaled to a consistent total. These normalized weights are then used in the final utility calculation.

Step 3: Final Utility Equations and Decision Rule

After transforming all external inputs (Step 1) and adjusting their weights according to salience and strategic orientation (Step 2), each politician computes two utility scores—one for accepting the proposal and one for rejecting it. These scores summarize how much support or opposition the politician perceives based on the weighted combination of all signals.

The utility for accepting the proposal is calculated as:

$$U_{accept} = W_U * U_t + W_S * S_t + W_M * M_t + W_D * D_{accept} + W_P * P_{accept} + W_{PP} * PP_{accept}$$

The Utility for rejecting the proposal is:

$$U_{reject} = -W_U * U_t - W_S * S_t - W_M * M_t + W_D * D_{reject} + W_P * P_{reject} + W_{PP} * PP_{reject}$$

Where:

- U_t, S_t, M_t are the transformed values of urban planner input, society sentiment, and media tone.
- $D_{accept}, P_{accept}, PP_{accept}$ are the positive components (if any) of NGO pressure, personal stance, and party stance.

- D_{reject} , P_{reject} , PP_{reject} are the corresponding negative components.
- W_i are the final normalized weights calculated in Step 2.

Note that the terms for planner, society, and media inputs appear with opposite signs in both utility functions. This reflects that positive values of those inputs boost acceptance and reduce rejection, while negative values have the reverse effect.

Once both utility scores are computed, the politician compares them. The final decision is determined by the difference between these two scores, subject to a minimum decisiveness threshold δ (e.g., 0.1). This threshold introduces a buffer zone to reflect real-world uncertainty or ambivalence.

- If: $U_{\text{accept}} > U_{\text{reject}} + \delta$, the proposal is accepted
- If: $U_{\text{reject}} > U_{\text{accept}} + \delta$, the proposal is rejected
- If: $|U_{\text{reject}} - U_{\text{accept}}| \leq \delta$, the proposal is sent for revision

This rule allows the model to represent decisive support or opposition while also accounting for cases where the politician perceives the proposal as ambiguous or controversial.

7.3.4 Stage 2 Peer Comparison and Adjustment

After computing their preliminary decision in Stage 1, politicians may revise their choice based on peer influence. Each politician compares their current decision with those of their peers, giving more weight to opinions from party-aligned or ideologically similar actors. This process adjusts individual decisions in light of social and organizational pressures, simulating the negotiation dynamics typical in local councils and parliaments.

For each politician, the influence of every other politician is computed using a party similarity score $\text{Sim}(P_i, P_j)$, where:

- $\text{Sim} = 1$ for same-party peers,
- $\text{Sim} < 1$ for peers from different parties, decreasing with ideological distance.

For each possible decision option (Accept, Reject, Revision), the model calculates the total weighted support from peers:

$$Support_{Decision}^i = \sum_{j \neq i, D_j = Decision} Sim(P_i, P_j)$$

The sum of supports across all options is normalized:

$$S_{total} = S_{Accept} + S_{Reject} + S_{Revision}$$

Based on these peer supports, each politician evaluates three possible actions:

- Stay with their current decision.
- Flip to the peer majority decision.
- Flip to another (non-majority) option.

The probability of each choice is proportional to peer support:

$$P_{flip_majority} = \frac{S_{majority}}{S_{total}} ; P_{stay} = \frac{S_{current}}{S_{total}} ; P_{flip_other} = \frac{S_{other}}{S_{total}}$$

A probabilistic draw determines whether the politician maintains their stance or adjusts it to align with peers. This adjustment mechanism captures dynamics where politicians may shift their position due to party cohesion, peer influence, or strategic alignment, while still preserving heterogeneity in responsiveness.

7.3.4 Final Decision Outcome

Once all politicians have made their individual decisions—after Stage 1 evaluation and Stage 2 peer adjustments—the final outcome of the simulation is determined through a simple majority vote.

Each politician's decision falls into one of three categories: Accept, Reject, or Request Revision of the development proposal. The final decision is computed by tallying the number of votes for each option:

- Accept votes
- Reject votes
- Revision votes

The option with the highest number of votes becomes the collective decision:

- If Accept receives the majority, the proposal is approved.
- If Reject prevails, the proposal is denied.
- If Revision gathers the most support, the proposal is sent back for revision.

This final decision marks the end of the simulation cycle, concluding the deliberation process for the given proposal.

8. Model Calibration, Sensitivity analysis and Validation

We have calibrated most of the core model components—society, politicians, NGOs, and media—using empirical data and stakeholder insights. The synthetic society was constructed with data from the Norwegian Citizen Panel and the Norwegian Citizen Survey, ensuring it reflects the real demographic and attitudinal composition. Politicians have been calibrated to real data as well, incorporating the exact number of politicians and their party affiliations. Stakeholders from the case study have provided information on each party's stance regarding environmental protection versus economic growth, as well as an index for ideological similarities between parties.

NGO attributes—such as experience and strategic orientation—are also calibrated based on empirical data, informed by stakeholder interviews with several NGO members. Finally, the media element is calibrated to empirical data on the number and tone of news items supporting or opposing each proposal, as reported by stakeholders. It is important to note that this calibration is not final and will be refined during the model validation phase.

Sensitivity analysis will proceed in two stages. First, we will analyze each core model component independently—NGOs, politicians, and society—by manually inputting their parameters. Media does not require extensive sensitivity testing because it involves only two parameters. In the second stage, we will conduct a comprehensive sensitivity analysis of the full model, where each component's actions and processes are driven by the simulation itself and interact dynamically. This sensitivity analysis also serves as a robustness check, helping us assess how stable and reliable the model outputs are when parameters are varied within plausible ranges. We have already completed the first-stage sensitivity analyses for NGOs and politicians (see Appendix 1 and 2). We have also developed a Shiny app that allows stakeholders and other users to explore the effects of parameter variation on political decision-making (<https://sim-lan-r-shinny-app.shinyapps.io/PoliticiansDecisionApp/>). The next steps will be to conduct the sensitivity analysis of society and, ultimately, the fully integrated model.

For validation, we will compare model outputs to real-world observations wherever possible—for example, the number of individuals joining NGOs, politicians' voting patterns, and the number and framing of media reports. In areas where data is missing, we will rely on expert and stakeholder input to validate the plausibility of the model. Stakeholder feedback will also be essential to ensure that the model's logic and outcomes are consistent with on-the-ground realities and context-specific insights. Finally, we acknowledge that the model may have some uncertainties or potential biases—particularly in areas where data is scarce or stakeholder views diverge. These limitations will be carefully documented and considered in interpreting model results.

9. Conclusion

This deliverable has outlined the construction and presented the implementation of the PRO-CLIMATE Multi-Agent Computer Model (MACM), developed within Task 5.2 as a central step in operationalizing the conceptual framework established in Task 5.1. Grounded in the Vestland case study, the MACM integrates psychological (HUMAT), sociological (MOA), and institutional logics to simulate complex, multi-actor dynamics around land use decisions and environmental governance. By incorporating diverse agents—citizens, NGOs, media, and politicians—within a robust, empirically-informed simulation architecture, the model will enable in-depth exploration of the behavioural, structural, and strategic conditions that may lead to climate-resilient transformations.

The goal is for the MACM to serve as both a testbed for scenario analysis and a tool for assessing systemic resilience. After additional validation, the model will allow stakeholders to experiment *in silico* with various policy and engagement strategies, probing the emergence of social tipping points and their dependence on specific actor constellations and contextual configurations. This aligns directly with Task 5.2's aims: not only to translate the conceptual underpinnings of behavioural change into an operational simulation, but also to provide a validated foundation for sensitivity analysis and cross-case comparison in future tasks.

The model's application to the Vestland context demonstrates its potential to reflect real-world diversity and decision dynamics while retaining generalizability. The model operates through time-stepped simulations in which agents interact, learn, and adapt based on changing internal states and external conditions, capturing the evolving nature of decision-making processes. As we move forward, this MACM will be extended, customized, and validated for additional living lab case studies, with simulation outputs informing the refinement of intervention strategies under varying socio-political and environmental conditions. To facilitate this, we propose a roadmap for generalizing the model to new case studies: we plan to use datasets available from Eurostat, such as EU-SILC (EU Statistics on Income and Living Conditions), to update synthetic population profiles for each case. Additionally, we will conduct targeted meetings and workshops with stakeholders from each case study to identify locally relevant elements, such as local datasets, NGO and media parameters, politicians, and the roles of other relevant stakeholders. This approach will allow us to systematically differentiate between case-specific and transferable elements, ensuring that the MACM framework remains robust and adaptable to diverse contexts. The results will feed into subsequent stages of WP5, ultimately contributing to the development of an interactive policy support platform designed to help stakeholders and decision-makers navigate pathways toward systemic climate resilience.

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Appendices

Appendix 1

Questions related to demographic variables

Education

Q409: What is your highest completed education?

Responses:

Value	Category	N	% of valid
1	Primary education/elementary school/comprehensive school	789	9.4%
2	Upper secondary education (general/vocational)	1936	23.1%
3	Vocational education at a vocational school	1093	13.1%
4	Education at university/college	4553	54.4%
9996	NOW	32	

Gender: Sex (man/woman)

sex

Responses:

Value	Category	N	% of valid
1	Man	4487	52.2%
2	Woman	4112	47.8%
(The figures are not weighted)			

Political View

r29_bglrs: Personal placement on political left and right wing scale

In politics people often talk about the “left wing” and the “right wing.” Below is a scale where 0 represents those who are on the far left politically, while 10 represents those who are on the far right.

Where would you place yourself on such a scale?

Responses:

Value	Category	N	% valid
0	0 - Left wing	17	2.6%
1	1	51	7.9%
2	2	66	10.2%
3	3	78	12.1%

Value	Category	N	% valid
4	4	44	6.8%
5	5	109	16.8%
6	6	76	11.7%
7	7	96	14.8%
8	8	69	10.7%
9	9	25	3.9%
10	10 - Right wing	16	2.5%
Sysmiss		9452	
(Unweighted numbers)			

Age:Age

Responses:

Value	Category	N	% of valid
1	18-24 years	566	6.6%
2	25-34 years	996	11.6%
3	35-49 years	1532	17.8%
4	50-66 years	2208	25.7%
5	67- years	3297	38.3%
(The figures are not weighted)			

Questions related to motives.**Motive “Climate Concern”**r28_pcwcc: How worried are you about climate change?

Responses:

Value	Category	N	% valid
1	Not at all worried	488	4.8%
2	Not very worried	1390	13.8%
3	Somewhat worried	2871	28.5%
4	Worried	3390	33.6%
5	Very worried	1947	19.3%
97	Not answered	156	

Motive “Nature Degradation”

r28_cewna: How worried are you about the degradation of nature?

Responses:

Value	Category	N	% valid
1	Not at all worried	25	1.2%
2	Not very worried	180	8.7%
3	Somewhat worried	537	25.9%
4	Worried	721	34.8%
5	Very worried	611	29.5%
97	Not answered	36	
98	Not asked	8132	

Motive “Growth-First Belief”

r29_pcgro: Agree/disagree: Economic growth should be ... e conflict with environmental interests.

To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements:

Economic growth should be safeguarded through the development of industry, even if it comes into conflict with environmental interests.

Responses:

Value	Category	N	% valid
1	Strongly agree	409	4.1%
2	Agree	1044	10.4%
3	Agree somewhat	2231	22.2%
4	Neither agree nor disagree	1040	10.4%
5	Disagree somewhat	2258	22.5%
6	Disagree	1928	19.2%
7	Strongly disagree	1125	11.2%
97	Not answered	64	
(Unweighted numbers)			

Motive “Economic Security”

r29_pceco: Assessment of: Your own financial situation today

How would you assess your own financial situation today?

Responses:

Value	Category	N	% valid
1	Very good	1058	10.5%
2	Good	4404	43.8%
3	Quite good	1956	19.4%

Value	Category	N	% valid
4	Neither good nor bad	1453	14.4%
5	Quite bad	803	8%
6	Bad	301	3%
7	Very bad	83	0.8%
97	Not answered	41	
(Unweighted numbers)			

Questions related to abilities and opportunities

Q509: How confident are you in your own abilities to participate in politics?

Responses:

Value	Category	N	% of valid
0	0 Not safe at all	208	7.8%
1	1	73	2.7%
2	2	119	4.4%
3	3	164	6.1%
4	4	174	6.5%
5	5	358	13.3%
6	6	261	9.7%
7	7	385	14.3%
8	8	300	11.2%
9	9	153	5.7%
10	10 Completely safe	244	9.1%
99	Don't know / No idea	244	9.1%
9996	NOW	16	
Sysmiss		5900	
(The figures are not weighted)			

Q510: To what extent would you say that political ... influence on what the authorities do?

To what extent would you say that the political system in Norway gives people like you influence over what the authorities do?

Responses:

Value	Category	N	% of valid
0	0 Not at all	331	12.4%
1	1	109	4.1%
2	2	204	7.6%
3	3	322	12%
4	4	281	10.5%

Value	Category	N	% of valid
5	5	353	13.2%
6	6	291	10.9%
7	7	313	11.7%
8	8	207	7.7%
9	9	64	2.4%
10	10 To a very large extent	62	2.3%
99	Don't know / No idea	138	5.2%
9996	NOW	13	
Sysmiss		5911	
<i>(The figures are not weighted)</i>			

Q511: Have you done the following in the last 12 months?

Q511_1

Have you done the following in the last 12 months?

Have you done the following in the last 12 months?

Voted in the last municipal election

Multiple answers possible

Value	Category
--------------	-----------------

0	0
---	---

1	Voted in the last municipal election
---	--------------------------------------

Q511_2

Have you done the following in the last 12 months?

Have you done the following in the last 12 months?

Contacted a politician or public official about issues that have concerned you

Multiple answers possible

Value	Category
--------------	-----------------

0	0
---	---

1	Contacted a politician or public official about issues that have concerned you
---	--

Q511_3

Have you done the following in the last 12 months?

Have you done the following in the last 12 months?

Attended a meeting of a trade union or political party

Multiple answers possible

Value	Category
0	0
1	Attended a meeting of a trade union or political party

Q511_4

Have you done the following in the last 12 months?

Have you done the following in the last 12 months?

Participated in a public hearing

Multiple answers possible

Value	Category
0	0
1	Participated in a public hearing

Q511_5

Have you done the following in the last 12 months?

Have you done the following in the last 12 months?

Stood for election or held a political office

Multiple answers possible

Value	Category
0	0
1	Stood for election or held a political office

Q511_6

Have you done the following in the last 12 months?

Have you done the following in the last 12 months?

Voted in a referendum

Multiple answers possible

Value	Category
0	0
1	Voted in a referendum

Q511_7

Have you done the following in the last 12 months?

Have you done the following in the last 12 months?

Participated in a public demonstration

Multiple answers possible

Value	Category
0	0
1	Participated in a public demonstration

Q511_8

Have you done the following in the last 12 months?

Have you done the following in the last 12 months?

Written during a petition (including online)

Multiple answers possible

Value	Category
0	0
1	Written during a petition (including online)

Q511_9

Have you done the following in the last 12 months?

Have you done the following in the last 12 months?

Shared a political viewpoint on social media like Facebook or X (formerly Twitter)?

Multiple answers possible

Value	Category
0	0
1	Shared a political viewpoint on social media like Facebook or X (formerly Twitter)?

Q511_10

Have you done the following in the last 12 months?

Have you done the following in the last 12 months?

Boycotted a product for political reasons

Multiple answers possible

Value	Category
0	0
1	Boycotted a product for political reasons

Q511_11

Have you done the following in the last 12 months?

Have you done the following in the last 12 months?

On a voluntary basis, you are involved in a social or environmental cause.

Multiple answers possible

Value	Category
0	0
1	On a voluntary basis, you are involved in a social or environmental cause.

Q511_12

Have you done the following in the last 12 months?

Have you done the following in the last 12 months?

No, didn't do any of this.

Multiple answers possible

Value	Category
0	0
1	No, didn't do any of this.

Q511_13

Have you done the following in the last 12 months?

Have you done the following in the last 12 months?

Don't want to answer

Multiple answers possible

Value	Category
0	0
1	Don't want to answer

Q416: Are you an active member of any of the following types of associations/organizations?

Q416_1

Are you an active member of any of the following types of associations/organizations? Multiple answers possible

Are you an active member of any of the following types of associations/organizations?

Charity

Multiple answers possible

Value	Category
0	0
1	Charity

Q416_2

Are you an active member of any of the following types of associations/organizations? Multiple answers possible

Are you an active member of any of the following types of associations/organizations?

Sports teams

Multiple answers possible

Value	Category
0	0
1	Sports teams

Q416_3

Are you an active member of any of the following types of associations/organizations? Multiple answers possible

Are you an active member of any of the following types of associations/organizations?

Political party

Multiple answers possible

Value	Category
0	0
1	Political party

Q416_4

Are you an active member of any of the following types of associations/organizations? Multiple answers possible

Are you an active member of any of the following types of associations/organizations?

Trade union

Multiple answers possible

Value	Category
0	0
1	Trade union

Q416_5

Are you an active member of any of the following types of associations/organizations? Multiple answers possible

Are you an active member of any of the following types of associations/organizations?

Singing/music society/club

Multiple answers possible

Value	Category
0	0
1	Singing/music society/club

Q416_6

Are you an active member of any of the following types of associations/organizations? Multiple answers possible

Are you an active member of any of the following types of associations/organizations?

Other associations/organizations

Multiple answers possible

Value	Category
0	0
1	Other associations/organizations

Q416_7

Are you an active member of any of the following types of associations/organizations? Multiple answers possible

Are you an active member of any of the following types of associations/organizations?

The Church of Norway (formerly the state church)

Multiple answers possible

Value	Category
0	0
1	The Church of Norway (formerly the State Church)

Q416_8

Are you an active member of any of the following types of associations/organizations? Multiple answers possible

Are you an active member of any of the following types of associations/organizations?

Other religious communities/life philosophy organizations

Multiple answers possible

Value	Category
0	0
1	Other religious communities/life philosophy organizations

Q416_9998

Are you an active member of any of the following types of associations/organizations? Multiple answers possible

Are you an active member of any of the following types of associations/organizations?

None of these

Multiple answers possible

Value	Category
0	0
1	None of these

r29 bqday: Which of the following descriptions best ... have been doing for the last seven days?

Responses:

Value	Category	N	% valid
1	In full-time paid work (or on temporary leave such as vacation leave or leave of absence/maternity leave)	960	44.1%
2	In part-time paid work (or on temporary leave such as vacation leave or leave of absence/maternity leave) with working h	78	3.6%
3	In part-time paid work (or on temporary leave such as vacation leave or leave of absence/maternity leave) with working h	75	3.4%
4	Self-employed	86	4%
5	In education (not paid by an employer)	53	2.4%
6	Unemployed and actively seeking a job	24	1.1%
7	Unemployed and not actively seeking a job	6	0.3%
8	Permanently ill or disabled	126	5.8%
9	Retired	754	34.6%
10	In military service	0	
11	Working at home, minding children or providing care to other persons	3	0.1%
12	Other:	12	0.6%
97	Not answered	46	
98	Not asked	7876	
(Unweighted numbers)			

r28 ceact 1: Agree/disagree: Media stories about clim ... I sympathise with the climate activists.

Lately, there have been some media stories about climate activists throwing paint at artwork, gluing themselves to buildings, or stopping traffic. To what extent do you agree or disagree with these statements?

I sympathise with the climate activists.

Value	Category	N	% valid
1	Strongly agree	54	2.6%
2	Agree	160	7.8%
3	Agree somewhat	293	14.2%
4	Neither agree nor disagree	348	16.9%

Value	Category	N	% valid
5	Disagree somewhat	212	10.3%
6	Disagree	384	18.7%
7	Strongly disagree	607	29.5%
97	Not answered	52	
98	Not asked	8132	
(Unweighted numbers)			

r28 ceact 6: Agree/disagree: Media stories about climate activists: I am proud of the climate activists.

Lately, there have been some media stories about climate activists throwing paint at artwork, gluing themselves to buildings, or stopping traffic. To what extent do you agree or disagree with these statements?

I am proud of the climate activists.

Value	Category	N	% valid
1	Strongly agree	43	2.1%
2	Agree	100	4.9%
3	Agree somewhat	215	10.5%
4	Neither agree nor disagree	335	16.3%
5	Disagree somewhat	201	9.8%
6	Disagree	442	21.5%
7	Strongly disagree	721	35.1%
97	Not answered	53	
98	Not asked	8132	
(Unweighted numbers)			

r28 ceact 3: Agree/disagree: Media stories about climate activism is not good for the climate cause.

Lately, there have been some media stories about climate activists throwing paint at artwork, gluing themselves to buildings, or stopping traffic. To what extent do you agree or disagree with these statements?

I think such activism is not good for the climate cause.

Value	Category	N	% valid
1	Strongly agree	583	28.2%
2	Agree	469	22.7%
3	Agree somewhat	421	20.3%
4	Neither agree nor disagree	253	12.2%
5	Disagree somewhat	148	7.2%
6	Disagree	124	6%
7	Strongly disagree	71	3.4%
97	Not answered	41	
98	Not asked	8132	
(Unweighted numbers)			

r28 ceact 5: Agree/disagree: Media stories about clim ... ink such climate activism is ridiculous.

Lately, there have been some media stories about climate activists throwing paint at artwork, gluing themselves to buildings, or stopping traffic. To what extent do you agree or disagree with these statements?

I think such climate activism is ridiculous.

Value	Category	N	% valid
1	Strongly agree	470	22.9%
2	Agree	319	15.5%
3	Agree somewhat	295	14.4%
4	Neither agree nor disagree	345	16.8%
5	Disagree somewhat	208	10.1%
6	Disagree	246	12%
7	Strongly disagree	172	8.4%
97	Not answered	55	
98	Not asked	8132	
(Unweighted numbers)			

Appendix 2

This appendix documents the results of the sensitivity analysis conducted for NGO actions in the PRO-CLIMATE MACM. It explores how changes in key organizational attributes (such as resources, experience, and strategy) and external factors (like cultural trust) affect the frequency and intensity of NGO actions, including direct actions, indirect actions, protests, and disruptive protests. All parameter thresholds and ranges in this sensitivity analysis reflect the initial expert-informed values used in the main model and will be refined during stakeholder-based calibration.

Parameters Explored

- Political System: [Open]
- Cultural Trust: 0 to 1, in 0.2 increments
- Resources: 0 to 1, in 0.2 increments
- Experience: 0 to 10, in 2-unit increments
- Strategy: 0 to 1, in 0.2 increments
- Lambda Factor: [0.05, 0.15, 0.3]
- Protest Size: [0.1, 0.5, 1.0]
- Disruptive Protest Size: [0.1, 0.5, 1.0]

Measured Outputs for Each Action

1. Total number of actions performed.
2. Average intensity values across all actions.

3. Cumulative intensity of all actions.

Simulation Design

Simulations are run over 12 timesteps, each representing one month. At each timestep, NGOs evaluate whether the conditions for an action are met. If so, an action is performed.

Overview of the results

While this setup works well for modeling indirect actions (e.g., media campaigns), it can result in unrealistically high frequencies for other actions such as direct actions and (disruptive) protests. Specifically, because the enabling conditions are fixed and do not vary across timesteps, once they exceed the action thresholds, NGOs may continue to act at every timestep. This could lead to 12 protests/disruptive protests or direct actions per year—one per month—which is likely an overestimate given the organizational and logistical demands of such activities. In contrast, performing 12 news-related actions annually remains plausible and I believe it may align more realistically with NGO communication efforts.

Below, I present graphs displaying the number of actions, average intensity, and cumulative intensity across the explored parameter space for each type of NGO action.

DIRECT ACTIONS

As expected, direct actions occur only when specific conditions are met—namely, Cultural Trust (CT) ≥ 0.5 , Resources ≥ 0.6 , and Experience ≥ 3 (see bottom-right panel in the graph below). Furthermore, as the strategy parameter becomes more antagonistic (higher values on the x-axis), the likelihood of a direct action decreases, reflecting the reduced probability of engagement under confrontational approaches.

Figure 7 Average number of direct actions

Restricting the parameter space to instances where the enabling conditions are met provides a more detailed view of how the number of direct actions varies across different parameter values (Figure 2).

Figure 8 Average number of direct actions within the restricted parameter space.

Fig 3 shows the average intensity of direct actions (eq 1) across varying values of strategy, experience, resources, and cultural trust.

$$D_{intensity} = \frac{5CT + 10R + 8E}{5 + 10 + 8} \quad eq. 1$$

Since cultural trust (CT), resources (R), and experience (E) are held constant, the average intensity is the same for all actions and there is no variation. As expected, higher levels of experience and resources yield higher average intensity values. Additionally, intensity increases with higher cultural trust (as shown by the separation of red, green, and blue dots). The flat lines across the x-axis confirm that strategy has no impact on intensity—it only affects whether the action is performed, not how intense it is once performed.

Figure 9 Average Intensity of Direct Actions Across Parameter Space

Figure 4 reveals how cumulative intensity (eq. 2) varies due to the interplay between action frequency and the saturation effect introduced by the λ parameter.

$$D_{cumulative} = I_{highest} + (1 - I_{highest}) * (1 - e^{-\lambda \sum_{i=2}^n I_i}) \quad eq. 2$$

At low strategy values (below 0.3), NGOs tend to perform actions at every timestep—up to 12 actions per year. This high frequency pushes cumulative intensity toward its upper bound, especially when λ is high. These effects are amplified when experience, resources, and cultural trust are also high, resulting in consistently elevated cumulative intensity values. However, as strategy becomes more antagonistic (>0.3), the number of actions drops sharply, leading to significantly lower cumulative intensities. This decline limits the impact of additional actions, as the saturation function dampens their contribution. Nevertheless, when resources, experience, and cultural trust are all at their maximum, even just two actions (e.g., at strategy = 0.8) can generate a cumulative intensity close to 1, indicating high effectiveness despite lower frequency.

Figure 10 Cumulative Intensity of Direct Actions Across Parameter Space

INDIRECT ACTIONS

Across all strategy values, Figure 5 shows that NGOs consistently perform the maximum number of indirect actions—12 per year—whenever the minimum resource threshold (≥ 0.1) is met. This reflects the low activation barrier for indirect actions, which only require minimal levels of resources, experience, and cultural trust. As a result, NGOs will always produce news content as long as they meet the resource threshold. However, this approach currently treats all indirect actions uniformly, without distinguishing between online news (e.g., Facebook, X, TikTok) and traditional media news. For greater realism, I propose modeling traditional media news as probabilistic, where the probability of producing a media news item equals the resource level, starting at 0.1. This captures the increased effort, access, and cost associated with reaching traditional media channels compared to online platforms.

Additionally, it is important to note that the creation of a news item does not guarantee its reception or impact. Whether individuals receive the news and adjust their motive importance accordingly is

governed by a separate probability, as described in the model documentation (see Section 6 in *News and Importance of Motives*).

Figure 11 Total Number of Indirect Actions Across Parameter Space

PROTEST ACTIONS

Figure 6 shows the total number of calls for protest actions, conditional on meeting the minimum resource threshold (≥ 0.2). When resources are below this level, no protests are triggered. For higher resource values, protest frequency depends heavily on the strategy parameter: at values ≥ 0.5 , protest calls occur deterministically whenever the enabling conditions are satisfied, resulting in the maximum number of actions (12 per year). However, when strategy is below 0.5, protest activation becomes probabilistic, which leads to a wider spread in the number of actions across runs (strategy values of 0.2 and 0.4). These results illustrate how even well-resourced NGOs may engage in fewer protests if their strategy leans toward less confrontational approaches.

Figure 12 Total Number of Protest Actions Across the parameter space

Figure 7 shows the average intensity (eq. 3) of protest actions across different values of strategy, experience, resources, and protest size.

$$P_{intensity} = \frac{5R + 5E + 10S}{5 + 5 + 10} \quad eq.3$$

Protest size has the strongest influence on average intensity, with larger protests (blue points) yielding consistently higher intensity values compared to smaller protests (red points). However, experience and resources also exert a secondary effect: higher values of experience and resources are associated with slightly higher average intensities across all protest sizes. Strategy does not affect the intensity itself, only the likelihood and frequency of protests (as seen in Figure 6).

Figure 13 Average Intensity of Protest Actions Across the Parameter Space.

Figure 8 shows the cumulative intensity (eq. 4) of protest actions across varying levels of experience, resources, strategy, protest size, and λ (saturation factor).

$$P_{cumulative} = I_{highest} + (1 - I_{highest}) * (1 - e^{-\lambda \sum_{i=2}^n I_i}) \quad eq.4$$

As expected, protest size remains the strongest driver of cumulative intensity: larger protests (blue) consistently produce higher cumulative values than smaller protests (red). However, experience and resources also contribute: higher levels of these parameters shift the cumulative intensity upwards across all protest sizes. The impact of strategy is clearly visible: at lower strategy values (~0.2–0.4), protest actions are less frequent, leading to higher cumulative intensities. As strategy becomes more antagonistic, more actions occur, increasing the cumulative effect. Additionally, λ modulates the extent of cumulative buildup, with higher λ values causing quicker saturation and thus leading to cumulative intensities that approach 1 even with fewer actions.

Values for strategies 0.8 and 1.0 are omitted because they are identical to those at 0.6 (12 protests), and strategy = 0 is omitted since it produces no protests.

Figure 14 Cumulative Intensity of Protest Actions Across the Parameter Space.

Disruptive protests

Figure 9 shows the total number of disruptive protest actions across different strategy levels, conditional on meeting basic resource, experience, and cultural trust thresholds. Disruptive protests require resources ≥ 0.2 but do not depend on political openness or trust levels. Disruptive actions occur deterministically when strategy ≥ 0.8 , leading to 12 actions per year. Below this threshold, actions are triggered probabilistically, resulting in fewer and more variable actions, particularly at strategy values of 0.2, 0.4, and 0.6.

Figure 15 Total Number of Disruptive Protest Actions Across Strategy The Parameter Space.

Figure 10 and 11 shows the average intensity and cumulative intensity (eq. 3 and 4) of disruptive protest actions across different values of strategy, experience, resources, and protest size. Because they follow the same equations, results are the same as those for protests (Figure 7 and 8).

Figure 16 Average Intensity of Disruptive Protest Actions Across the Parameter Space

Figure 17 Cumulative Intensity of Disruptive Protest Actions Across the Parameter Space.

Overall, this analysis provides valuable insights into how NGO attributes and external factors shape the landscape of actions within the PRO-CLIMATE simulation. Future model refinement and validation will draw on these findings, stakeholder feedback, and empirical data to ensure realistic and context-sensitive results.

Appendix 3

This appendix presents the results of sensitivity analyses for the politician decision-making component of the PRO-CLIMATE model. These analyses examine how external factors (such as planner input, NGO pressure, societal feedback, and media tone) and internal factors (such as party influence and personal stance) shape the final decisions of politicians. Two sets of scenarios

are included: one without party and personal influences, and one with them. These analyses help assess the robustness of the decision-making logic, providing insights into how different constellations of political, social, and media pressures can lead to different policy outcomes.

Politician Decision Process: Stage 1 and Stage 2

The politician’s decision unfolds in two distinct stages:

- Stage 1: Individual Utility-Based Evaluation
Each politician independently evaluates an infrastructure proposal based on a weighted utility function. This function integrates inputs such as urban planner assessments, NGO pressure, public sentiment, media tone, personal stance, and party position (Table 1). The outcome is a preliminary decision: *accept, reject, revise, or tie*.
- Stage 2: Peer Influence Adjustment
Politicians then reconsider their preliminary decision by observing how peers have voted. This peer influence is weighted by party similarity, and decisions may shift probabilistically based on the distribution of peer support for each option. The result of this stage is the politician’s final decision.

Parameter Space explored and Interpretations

Parameter	Symbol	Range / Values	Meaning
Environmental Framing Level	EFL	0 to 1 (continuous)	Degree to which urban planner inputs are ignored: 0 = fully used, 1 = fully disregarded
Urban Planner Inputs	UP1, UP2, UP3	0, 0.5, 1	Planner support: 0 = oppose, 1 = support, 0.5 = neutral
NGO Pressure	D	-1 to 1	Pressure: -1 = full opposition, 1 = full support
Society Feedback	S	0, 0.5, 1	Population sentiment: 0 = oppose, 1 = support, 0.5 = neutral
Media Tone	M	0, 0.5, 1	Dominant media framing tone: 0 = oppose, 1 = support, 0.5 = neutral
Salience Media	salM	0, 0.5, 1	Media visibility (coverage volume): 0= no visibility, 0.5 medium visibility, 1 = highest visibility
Salience Society	salS	0, 0.5, 1	Visibility of societal feedback (e.g., protest size) 0= no visibility, 0.5 medium visibility, 1 = highest visibility
Planner Alignment	–	"Neg-Neg-Neg" to "Pos-Pos-Pos"	Combined classification of the three Urban Planners inputs (e.g., "Neutral-Pos-Neg")

Input Weights

The weights assigned to different inputs remain constant throughout the simulation. These weights reflect the relative importance of each input in shaping a politician’s utility function during proposal evaluation.

Input	Symbol	Baseline	Rationale
Urban Planner 1	W_{U1}	0.11	Urban planners provide authoritative but procedural input. Their influence is always relevant but typically limited at the decision stage—especially if the issue has already been framed.
Urban Planner 2	W_{U2}	0.11	
Urban Planner 3	W_{U3}	0.11	
NGO Pressure	W_D	0.11	NGOs exert structured advocacy pressure, often grounded in expertise or activism. Their influence is significant but tends to target specific causes.
Society Feedback	W_S	0.17	Citizens' views can have strong political implications—especially during high-salience events. This is capped as a high-impact input, modulated
Media Tone	W_M	0.17	Media influences both public sentiment and elite attention. Its framing power is strong, especially when coverage is extensive. Like society, this is modulated.

Input	Symbol	Baseline	Rationale
Personal Stance	W_P	0.0	The politician's own values play a consistent but bounded role.
Party Stance	W_{PP}	0.0	Party lines guide decisions

Results with No Party/Personal influence

In this analysis, each parameter combination is replicated 10 times to ensure consistency and allow for the detection of stochastic variation if present.

However, these scenarios are fully deterministic. There is no influence from party stance or personal ideology, as their respective weights are explicitly set to zero. As a result, all politicians are exposed to the same decision-making inputs and use the same evaluation criteria. This means we expect all politicians to make the same decision in each replication. Consequently, the proportion of any given decision outcome is always 1 within a run. This setup allows us to isolate and better understand how the external factors—such as planner input, NGO pressure, media tone, and societal feedback—shape collective outcomes. In this case, we get an overall nice split between Accept/Reject and a smaller proportion of Revise decisions.

Figure 18. Relative Frequency of Winning Decisions with no party/personal influence.

Graph Description: Dominant Decision Outcomes in Politician Sensitivity Analysis

These graphs visualize the distribution of dominant winning decisions (e.g., accept, revise, reject, or tie) made by politicians under different parameter configurations in the model. The visualization layout captures how decisions are influenced by the interplay of urban planner alignment, public/media support, and salience.

Data Subsetting:

Each individual plot corresponds to a unique combination of:

- EFL (Expert Framing Level): [0, 0.5, 1]
- NGO.Pressure: [-1, 0, 1]:

These combinations define the high-level context for how much planner input is trusted (via EFL) and whether NGOs are supportive or oppositional.

X-axis: Planner_Alignment

- Represents configurations of three Urban Planner assessments (U1, U2, U3), classified as Pos, Neg, or Neutral.

- Shows how alignment among experts affects dominant decisions.

Y-axis: Decision Category

- Four decision outcomes, shown top-to-bottom:
 - "accept" (4)
 - "revise" (3)
 - "tie" (2)
 - "reject" (1)

Inside Each (x, y) Cell: Dot Encoding

Each cell (defined by a specific planner alignment and decision outcome) contains up to 9 dots, representing all combinations of salience conditions.

- Increasing media salience
 - Left to right: left = no visibility in media, right = max visibility
 - Fill color: red = none, yellow = medium, green = max
- Increasing societal salience
 - Top to bottom: top = no public attention, bottom = max public attention
 - Shape: circle = none, square = medium, triangle = max
- Winning decision
 - Size: how often this decision was dominant across replications (larger dots = more frequent)
 - Transparency: also reflects frequency (darker dots = more dominant)

Together, this layout makes it easy to see which conditions consistently lead to a particular decision and how visibility in society and media affect that outcome (see table below).

Saliency Media:none Saliency Society: none					
Saliency Media:none Saliency Society: middle					
Saliency Media:none Saliency Society: max					

Faceting

X-facet: Society Feedback

- Level of societal support. Labels include the raw value + interpretation: e.g., "Soc.Feedback 0.5 (neutral)"

Y-facet: Media Tone:

- Level of media favorability. Also labeled with numeric + interpretation, e.g., "Media.Tone 1.00 (accept)"

Scenario 1: No Planner Influence (EFL = 1) & Neutral NGO Pressure (0)

This scenario isolates the influence of media and society, as both planners and NGOs exert no weight. Decisions shift cleanly with Media Tone and Society Feedback: more favorable tone or support pushes decisions from reject to revise and eventually to accept. Planner alignment is irrelevant, and variation comes entirely from the public and media dimensions—this is the cleanest expression of their joint impact.

D5.2 Multi-Agent Computer Model

Figure 19. Scenario 1: No planner Influence & Neutral NGO pressure

Scenario 2: No Planner Influence (EFL = 1) & Full NGO Support (1)

With planners ignored and NGOs fully supporting the proposal, decisions are overwhelmingly “accept”, especially as media and society move from neutral to supportive. The x-axis (planner alignment) remains irrelevant. Rejections only persist in the top-left corner where all other actors strongly oppose. Overall, NGO support dominates the decision space in the absence of planner influence.

D5.2 Multi-Agent Computer Model

Figure 20. Scenario 2: No Planner Influence and Full NGO support

Scenario 3: No Planner Influence (EFL = 1) & Full NGO Opposition (-1)

With planners fully disregarded (EFL = 1), the decision patterns are driven entirely by NGO pressure, media tone, and societal feedback. As expected, most decisions are rejections, reflecting the strong negative stance of NGOs. The x-axis (planner alignment) has no effect, and variation emerges only when media and society are both highly supportive—in which case we start to see some “revise” or “accept” outcomes, particularly in the lower-right panel (Media = 1, Society = 1).

D5.2 Multi-Agent Computer Model

Figure 21. Scenario 3: No Planner Influence & Full NGO Opposition

Scenario 4: Partial Planner Influence (EFL = 0.5) & Neutral NGO Pressure (0)

This scenario closely mirrors Scenario 3, where NGO pressure is neutral and planners had full influence. The main difference here is that with planner input dampened (EFL = 0.5), the effects of media tone and societal feedback become slightly more visible. In particular, “revise” decisions appear in more configurations, especially when planner alignment is mixed. While the overall decision patterns remain consistent, this shift confirms that reducing expert influence gives greater weight to public and media sentiment.

Figure 22. Scenario 4: Partial Planner Influence & Neutral NGO Pressure

Scenario 5: Partial Planner Influence (EFL = 0.5) & Full NGO Support (+1)

In this scenario, the expert framing level is set to 0.5, meaning that urban planner input is only partially considered by politicians. At the same time, NGOs are fully supportive of the proposal. This configuration allows us to explore how decisions are shaped when planners are de-emphasized and external public-facing signals—media tone, societal feedback, and NGO pressure—gain more weight in the outcome.

We observe a clear shift toward the “accept” decision across a wide range of planner alignments. The dominance of “accept” becomes even stronger as society and media support increase, particularly in the bottom-right panels where both are favorable. In these cells, even planner alignments that are negative tend to result in acceptance.

In contrast, rejections are mostly limited to configurations where planner alignment is negative, and both media and societal support are weak—especially in the top-left panels. However, the frequency and dominance of “reject” decisions are visibly reduced compared to scenarios with NGO opposition.

Importantly, with planners contributing only moderately (EFL = 0.5), the influence of media and society becomes more prominent. You can see that increases in saliency levels (represented by shape and color) correlate with a rising occurrence of “accept” even when planner support is lacking or mixed. The middle row of facets, representing neutral media tone, displays a wide variety of decisions depending on saliency and planner configuration—indicating that small contextual shifts can tip the decision one way or the other when planners are not the dominant input.

This scenario illustrates that when NGO pressure is strongly positive, and planner input is dampened, public and media dynamics become decisive. It highlights the power of public discourse in shaping political outcomes when expert advice is only partially trusted.

Figure 23. Scenario 5: Partial Planner Influence & Full NGO Support.

Scenario 6: Partial Planner Influence (EFL = 0.5) & Full NGO Opposition (-1)

In this configuration, urban planner input is partially considered in the politician's decision-making (EFL = 0.5), and NGOs are strongly opposing the proposal. This setup provides a useful contrast to Scenarios 1 and 3, allowing us to observe how planner influence interacts with negative NGO pressure and how decisions shift when that expert influence is weakened but not eliminated. Compared to Scenario 1 (where EFL = 0), we observe a slight softening of the rejection dominance. While reject remains the dominant decision in many configurations—especially when planner alignment is negative, society/media feedback are low, and salience is weak—we now begin to see more revision and acceptance outcomes appear as media/society becomes more positive.

The central panels (where society and media feedback are neutral) show greater variability in dominant decisions compared to the previous scenario. For instance:

- When planner alignment is positive (e.g., Neutral-Pos-Pos or Pos-Pos-Pos), the accept decision appears less frequently than when EFL = 0.
- When planners are neutral and both media/society are negative, the reject outcome still dominates, suggesting NGO pressure has a strong anchoring effect unless planners and other sources align positively.

In the bottom-right panel (both media and society strongly favor acceptance), we continue to see an increased frequency of "accept", even when planners are moderately aligned around negative assessment. This suggests that when external pressures are strong and positive, partial planner trust can hardly allow those pressures to tip the outcome, unless all of them are aligned along the negative assessment.

In short, this scenario demonstrates a more nuanced decision landscape. Partial trust in planners introduces greater decision diversity, where outcomes are sensitive to the combined influence of planners, salience, and public/media tone.

Figure 24. Scenario 6: Partial Planner Influence & Full NGO Opposition.

Scenario 7: Full Input of Planners (EFL = 0) & Neutral NGO Pressure (NGO = 0)

In this scenario, the influence of NGOs is removed by setting their pressure to zero. Combined with full consideration of planner input (EFL = 0), this configuration allows us to clearly observe how public opinion, media tone, salience, and planner alignment shape decisions when NGOs play no role in the deliberation.

Unlike the previous two scenarios, decisions here exhibit greater variation. With no directional push from NGOs, the balance between planner alignment and external cues (media and societal attitudes) becomes more delicate and situational. This results in more nuanced outcomes, including a higher frequency of revise decisions, especially in the center panels.

Patterns observed:

- When planner support is positive (Pos-Pos-Pos or similar), decisions tend to be accept, particularly when either media tone or society feedback is supportive, even if not both.
- Conversely, when planner support is weak or negative, rejections are still common, but less than in the NGO opposition scenario. The final outcome can be shifted by stronger salience and society/media support.
- Middle and neutral panels (e.g., media tone and society both neutral) reveal clusters of revise decisions, suggesting indecision when no input clearly dominates.

Saliency still matters:

- Across panels, the combinations of high salience in media and society often amplify whatever signal they convey. For example, if both salience values are high and tone/feedback are positive, acceptance dominates—even under mixed planner input.
- However, when salience is low or mixed, decisions follow planner alignment more closely, with external inputs playing a weaker role.

Overall, this scenario illustrates a tension-driven decision landscape where no actor dominates and outcomes emerge from the interaction of all forces. It highlights how planners and contextual salience jointly shape decisions under conditions of institutional neutrality.

Figure 25. Scenario 7: Full Input of Planners & Neutral NGO Pressure.

Scenario 8: Full Input of Planners (EFL = 0) & Full NGO Support (NGO = +1)

In this configuration, politicians fully consider the input of urban planners (EFL = 0), while NGOs are strongly supportive of the proposal. This creates a setting where expert knowledge and NGO pressure align positively toward acceptance. However, decisions are still sensitive to the influence of other external factors such as public opinion (Society Feedback), media tone, and the salience of these inputs.

Overall, decisions tend to be accept across most panels, especially in the right and center columns where society is neutral or supportive. When media and society strongly oppose the proposal (top-left panel), some reject or revise decisions still occur, especially when planners themselves are also negative.

The role of planner alignment remains visible: even with NGO support, when planners are aligned negatively (e.g., Neg-Neg-Neg or Neg-Neg-Neutral), rejections still happen in conditions of low public/media support.

However, compared to Scenario 1 (NGO = -1), the accept decisions here emerge more frequently and earlier—i.e., under less favorable societal/media settings.

The trend from top-left (low external support) to bottom-right (high support) again illustrates how external signals—when strongly positive—amplify the effect of NGO backing and planner input to yield nearly uniform accept outcomes. Yet, the presence of revision decisions in some mid-range scenarios (e.g., neutral media and society) suggests a more moderate deliberation in those contexts.

In short, NGO support helps tip the scale toward acceptance, but planner disagreement and strongly negative public/media tones can still temper or reverse the final decision.

Figure 26. Scenario 8: Full Input of Planners & Full NGO Support.

Scenario 9: Full Input of Planners (EFL = 0) & Full NGO Opposition (-1)

In this scenario, urban planner input is fully trusted (EFL = 0) and NGOs are uniformly opposed to the proposal (NGO.Pressure = -1). Politicians rely heavily on expert (planner) assessments, and the NGO pressure consistently acts against the proposal. Because these factors are deterministic and party/personal influences are disabled, all politicians vote identically for a given configuration. Observed Patterns

- Rejection is the dominant decision in most cells where any combination of planners, society, or media expresses opposition. Even if only one of these actors is oppositional, the weight of NGO opposition often tips the decision to reject.
- Planner alignment plays a strong role:
 - When planners are all negative or two out of three are negative, decisions overwhelmingly favor rejection, even when media and society strongly support the proposal.
 - When planners are all positive, the proposal is often accepted, unless both media and society are strongly opposed with high salience.
- Saliency of media and society matters, but only to a degree:
 - In panels where media tone and societal feedback are both neutral or positive, planner input becomes more decisive.
 - High salience from either media or society can counteract the other if that other’s salience is low or medium, but not when both are strongly negative.
- As we move from top-left to bottom-right in the grid, we move through a gradient of increasing external support (society and media tone shifting from reject → accept). Correspondingly, we observe a clear transition from reject → revise → accept decisions, particularly when planner alignment is neutral or supportive.
- Interestingly, even in the bottom-right panel—where both media and society fully support the proposal with high salience—rejection can still occur if planner alignment is strongly

negative, showing the powerful effect of expert framing when trusted (EFL = 0), especially combined with strong NGO opposition.

Conclusion

This scenario validates that when planner input is trusted and NGOs oppose, planner alignment becomes the most critical determinant. Even high public and media support cannot consistently override negative planner assessments. Decisions shift from rejection to acceptance as external opinion becomes more favorable, but this shift is conditional on expert alignment.

Figure 27. Scenario 9: Full Input of Planners & Full NGO Opposition

Results with Party/Personal influence

Parameter Space explored and Interpretations

Parameter	Symbol	Range / Values	Meaning
Environmental Framing Level	EFL	0 to 1 (continuous)	Degree to which urban planner inputs are ignored: 0 = fully used, 1 = fully disregarded
Urban Planner Inputs	UP1, UP2, UP3	0, 0.5, 1	Planner support: 0 = oppose, 1 = support, 0.5 = neutral
NGO Pressure	D	-1 to 1	Pressure: -1 = full opposition, 1 = full support
Society Feedback	S	0, 0.5, 1	Population sentiment: 0 = oppose, 1 = support, 0.5 = neutral
Media Tone	M	0, 0.5, 1	Dominant media framing tone: 0 = oppose, 1 = support, 0.5 = neutral
Saliency Media	salM	0, 0.5, 1	Media visibility (coverage volume): 0= no visibility, 0.5 medium visibility, 1 = highest visibility
Saliency Society	salS	0, 0.5, 1	Visibility of societal feedback (e.g., protest size) 0= no visibility, 0.5 medium visibility, 1 = highest visibility
Planner Alignment	—	"Neg-Neg-Neg" to "Pos-Pos-Pos"	Combined classification of the three Urban Planners inputs (e.g., "Neutral-Pos-Neg")

Input Weights

The weights assigned to different inputs remain constant throughout the simulation. These weights reflect the relative importance of each input in shaping a politician’s utility function during proposal evaluation.

Input	Symbol	Baseline	Rationale
Urban Planner 1	W_{U1}	0.11	Urban planners provide authoritative but procedural input. Their influence is always relevant but typically limited at the decision stage—especially if the issue has already been framed.
Urban Planner 2	W_{U2}	0.11	
Urban Planner 3	W_{U3}	0.11	
NGO Pressure	W_D	0.11	NGOs exert structured advocacy pressure, often grounded in expertise or activism. Their influence is significant but tends to target specific causes.
Society Feedback	W_S	0.17	Citizens' views can have strong political implications—especially during high-salience events. This is capped as a high-impact input, modulated
Media Tone	W_M	0.17	Media influences both public sentiment and elite attention. Its framing power is strong, especially when coverage is extensive. Like society, this is modulated.
Personal Stance	W_P	0.11	The politician’s own values play a consistent but bounded role.
Party Stance	W_{PP}	0.11	Party lines guide decisions

In this analysis, each parameter combination is replicated 10 times to ensure consistency and allow for the detection of stochastic variation if present. In contrast to the previous scenario, here there is influence from party stance or personal ideology. As a result, even though all politicians are exposed to the same external inputs, their party ideology and personal stance influence the decision-making and thus, not all make the same decisions. This is clearly observed when looking at the proportion of winning decisions from the whole parameter space (see figure below). Here we can clearly see that Accept wins in close to 60% of the cases. This confirms that most of the representatives belong to political parties (conservative and progress fulling supporting growth vs nature, with 17 representatives) that favor growth over nature, as clearly show in the data you guys provided me with.

Figure 28 Relative frequency of winning decisions with Party/Personal Influence

Scenario 1: No Planner Influence (EFL = 1) & Neutral NGO Pressure (0)

This graph isolates the influence of Media/society against party influence. Compare this graph to scenario 1 in the other file (no party influence). Accept happens much more frequently, and some dots become more transparent and with smaller size, meaning that in some cases, the dominant winning decision did not happen in all 10 replications.

Figure 29. Scenario 1: No Planner Influence & Neutral NGO Pressure

Scenario 2: No Planner Influence (EFL = 1) & Full NGO Support (1)

When the NGO fully supports the proposal, rejection rarely happens. This happens more likely when both society and media are against and saliency is medium/high.

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Figure 30. Scenario 2: No Planner Influence & Full NGO Support

Scenario 3: No Planner Influence (EFL = 1) & Full NGO Opposition (-1)

NGO is fully opposition, this tilts the balance towards rejection but still not at such a big rate as when there is no party influence

Decision Configuration | EFL = 1 | NGO.Pressure = -1

Y = Decision (grid) | Fill = Saliency.Media | Shape = Saliency.Society | Size/Alpha = Proportion

Figure 31. Scenario 3: No Planner Influence & Full NGO Opposition

Scenario 4: Partial Planner Influence (EFL = 0.5) & Neutral NGO Pressure (0)

Decision Configuration | EFL = 0.5 | NGO.Pressure = 0

Y = Decision (grid) | Fill = Saliency.Media | Shape = Saliency.Society | Size/Alpha = Proportion

Figure 32. Scenario 4: Partial Planner Influence & Neutral NGO Pressure

Scenario 5: Partial Planner Influence (EFL = 0.5) & Full NGO Support (+1)

Decision Configuration | EFL = 0.5 | NGO.Pressure = 1

Y = Decision (grid) | Fill = Saliency.Media | Shape = Saliency.Society | Size/Alpha = Proportion

Figure 33. Scenario 5: Partial Planner Influence & Full NGO Support

Scenario 6: Partial Planner Influence (EFL = 0.5) & Full NGO Opposition (-1)

Decision Configuration | EFL = 0.5 | NGO.Pressure = -1

Y = Decision (grid) | Fill = Saliency.Media | Shape = Saliency.Society | Size/Alpha = Proportion

Figure 34. Scenario 6: Partial Planner Influence & Full NGO Opposition

Scenario 8: Full Input of Planners (EFL = 0) & Full NGO Support (NGO = +1)

Decision Configuration | EFL = 0 | NGO.Pressure = 1

Y = Decision (grid) | Fill = Saliency.Media | Shape = Saliency.Society | Size/Alpha = Proportion

Figure 36. Scenario 8: Full Input of Planners & Full NGO Support.

Scenario 9: Full Input of Planners (EFL = 0) & Full NGO Opposition (-1)

Decision Configuration | EFL = 0 | NGO.Pressure = -1

Y = Decision (grid) | Fill = Saliency.Media | Shape = Saliency.Society | Size/Alpha = Proportion

Figure 37. Scenario 9: Full Input of Planners & Full NGO Opposition.

These findings provide valuable insights into how the interplay of expert input, civil society pressure, media framing, and political alignment shape policy outcomes in the simulation. They serve as a foundation for further model calibration and validation with stakeholder input, ensuring that the model remains grounded in real-world political dynamics while maintaining analytical flexibility. Future iterations of the model will refine these patterns further, incorporating feedback from stakeholders and updates to empirical data as they become available.